

Hochschule Neubrandenburg
University of Applied Sciences

**CLIMATE MULTI-TEMPORAL ANALYSIS WITH GOOGLE EARTH ENGINE FOR
THE RUFJI BASIN**

Master Thesis

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ABSTRACT

This research presents an extensive multi-temporal climate analysis using the advanced capabilities of Google Earth Engine (GEE) on The Rufiji Basin. Leveraging GEE's extensive satellite imagery and computational power, this study analyses climate variables such as temperature, precipitation, and vegetation dynamics over several decades. The Rufiji Basin, a critical watershed in Tanzania, faces significant climate-related challenges that necessitate comprehensive analysis for sustainable management and policy formulation.

The research employs a series of temporal analyses to identify trends, patterns, and anomalies in the climatic data. The methodology integrates time-series analysis of satellite data, climate model outputs, and ground-based observations to understand long-term climatic changes and their impacts on the Rufiji Basin's ecosystem and hydrology.

Significant findings from this study include the identification of a unimodal precipitation pattern where rainy season is only between November to May, with one maximum in January. Temperature trend is also unimodal with one maximum in October. Rainfall and temperature are drivers of water resources and vegetation changes in the basin. The analysis of vegetation indices reveals insights into land-cover changes and their relationship with climatic variables. Furthermore, the study is conducted entirely on Open-Source resources for analysis and publication.

This thesis not only contributes to the understanding of climate dynamics in the Rufiji Basin but also demonstrates the effectiveness of GEE as a tool for environmental monitoring and climate analysis. The findings provide valuable insights for policymakers, environmental managers, and local communities in developing adaptive strategies for climate resilience. The research also highlights the potential of satellite remote sensing and geospatial technologies in addressing complex environmental challenges in the context of developing countries.

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List of Abbreviations and Acronyms

AMSR-E - Advanced Microwave Scanning Radiometer for EOS
AMSU-A - Advanced Microwave Sounding Unit
API - Application Programming Interface
ASTER - Advanced Spaceborne Thermal and Reflection Radiometer
ASI - Agenzia Spaziale Italiana
AIRS - Atmospheric Infrared Sounder
BRDF - Bidirectional Reflectance Distribution Function
CERES - Advanced Microwave Scanning Radiometer for EOS
CHIRP - Climate Hazards group Infrared Precipitation
CHIRPS - Climate Hazards Group InfraRed Precipitation with Station data
CHPclim - Climate Hazards group Precipitation climatology
CMAP - Climate Prediction Centre's Merged Analysis of Precipitation
CMORPH - Climate Prediction Centre Morphing Technique
CCD - Cold Cloud Duration
CAB - Congo Air Boundary
CSV - Comma Separated Values
DEM - Digital Elevation Model
DLR - Deutsche Zentrum für Luft- und Raumfahrt e. V.
EOS - Earth Observing System
EOSDIS - Earth Observing System Data and Information System
EROS - Earth Resources Observation and Science
ECMWF - European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts
EnKF - Ensemble Kalman Filter
EU - European Union
GDEM - Global Digital Elevation Model
GOES - Geostationary Operational Environmental Satellites
GLAS - Geoscience Laser Altimeter System
GEE - Google Earth Engine
GeoTIFF - Geo Tag Image File Format
GIS - Geographic Information System
GPCC - Global Precipitation Climatology Centre
GRASS - Geographic Resources Analysis
GPD - Global Precipitation Dataset
GPM - Global Precipitation Measurement
HSB - Humidity Sounder for Brazil
ICESat - Ice, Cloud, and land Elevation Satellite
ITCZ - Intertropical Convergence Zone
JNHPP - Julius Nyerere Hydropower Plant
LP DAAC - Land Processes Distributed Active Archive Centre
LANCE - Land, Atmosphere Near Real-time Capability for EOS
LST - Land-surface temperature
MEaSURES - Making Earth System Data Records for Use in Research Environments
Meteosat - Meteorological Satellites
MISR - Multi-angle Imaging SpectroRadiometer
MODIS - Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer

MOPITT- Measurement of Pollution in the Troposphere
NBAR - Nadir-BRDF Adjusted Reflectance
NASA - National Aeronautics and Space Administration
NASA JPL - National Aeronautics and Space Administration Jet Propulsion Laboratory
NASADEM - National Aeronautics and Space Administration Digital Elevation Model
NGA - National Geospatial-Intelligence Agency
NIR - Near-Infrared
NDVI - Normalized Difference Vegetation Index
NDWI - Normalized Difference Water Index
NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration
OAuth - Open-standard Authorization
PRISM - Advanced Land Observing Satellite's Panchromatic Remote-sensing Instrument for Stereo Mapping
QGIS - Quantum GIS
REST API - Representational State Transfer
RMSE - Root Mean Square Error
SMAP - Soil Moisture Active Passive
SMOS - Soil Moisture Ocean Salinity
SPOT - Satellite pour l'Observation de la Terre
SRTM - Space Shuttle Radar Topography Mission
TMA - Tanzania Meteorological Association
TRMM - Tropical Rainfall Measuring Mission
UNESCO - United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization
UNICEF - United Nations International Children's Emergency Fund
USDA - United States Department of Agriculture
USGS - United States Geological Survey
WebGIS- Web Geographic Information System

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1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. Background to the Study

In recent years, the field of environmental monitoring and analysis has been significantly transformed by the advent of remote sensing technology. This technology has opened new avenues for understanding complex environmental phenomena, particularly in the realms of climate patterns and changes. Remote sensing data has become an invaluable resource for researchers, policymakers, and environmentalists alike.

However, despite the immense potential of remote sensing data, the current methods, and tools for time series analysis of climate using such data face several critical limitations. These limitations have hampered the ability to fully harness the power of this technology for comprehensive and timely analysis. The primary challenges are as follows:

Processing and analysing the vast volumes of remote sensing data often exceed the capabilities of traditional computing systems. The sheer size and complexity of these datasets demand innovative solutions to handle the computational demands efficiently.

Accessing and integrating diverse remote sensing data sources can be a cumbersome and time-consuming process. Researchers encounter hurdles related to data acquisition, compatibility, and availability, making it challenging to create holistic analyses.

As the volume of available remote sensing data continues to grow, scaling the analysis to accommodate this increasing influx of information presents a formidable challenge. Traditional methods struggle to keep pace with the expanding data resources.

These limitations underscore the urgent need for a more efficient and scalable approach to climate time series analysis using remote sensing data. Specifically, there is a compelling case for transitioning to a cloud-based solution that can leverage the extensive computational resources and storage capacities of the cloud environment to address these challenges effectively.

This research initiative seeks to bridge this gap by developing a robust, cloud-based framework tailored for climate time series analysis. The proposed framework will harness the power of remote sensing data, cloud computing infrastructure, and advanced analytical techniques to provide comprehensive and timely insights into weather, climate patterns and changes over time.

1.2. Statement of the Problem

Remote sensing is critical in understanding the environment, particularly in the context of climate patterns. However, the current methods and tools for time series analysis of climate using remote sensing data are not without their limitations. These limitations primarily revolve around computational constraints, data accessibility, and scalability issues.

The computational demands of processing and analysing large volumes of remote sensing data often exceed the capabilities of traditional computing systems. Furthermore, accessing and integrating diverse remote sensing data sources can be a complex and time-consuming process. Lastly, the ability to scale the analysis to accommodate increasing volumes of data remains a significant challenge.

These limitations underscore the need for a more efficient and scalable approach to climate time series analysis using remote sensing data. Specifically, there is a pressing need for a cloud-based solution that can leverage the vast computational resources and storage capacities of the cloud to overcome these challenges.

This research aims to address this gap by developing a robust, cloud-based framework for climate time series analysis. The proposed framework will harness the power of remote sensing data, cloud computing infrastructure, and advanced analytics to provide comprehensive and timely analysis of climate changes over time.

The research will explore novel methods for data acquisition, processing, integration, and analysis, with a particular focus on scalability, efficiency, and accuracy. The outcomes of this research will not only enhance understanding of climate dynamics and environmental changes but also provide valuable insights for informed decision-making in the context of land use planning and natural resource management.

1.3. Objectives

The primary objective is to design and develop a scalable and efficient cloud-based framework that integrates remote sensing data, cloud computing infrastructure, and advanced analytical techniques for climate time series analysis.

This research aims to explore methods for acquiring and preprocessing remote sensing data, including satellite imagery and climate datasets, ensuring data quality and compatibility for long-term time series analysis.

The objective is to investigate climate patterns and trends using remote sensing data, focusing on variables such as temperature, precipitation, evapotranspiration, and vegetation indices. This involves developing algorithms and models to analyse climate data at different temporal and spatial scales.

The goal is to develop algorithms and techniques for detecting and monitoring climate changes over time using remote sensing imagery. This includes identifying and classifying different climate parameters, quantifying changes, and analysing their spatial and temporal dynamics.

The research aims to explore methods for integrating climate data to investigate the relationship between climate patterns and land cover changes. This involves analysing how climate variables influence land cover and assessing the impact of land cover changes on local climate conditions.

The objective is to validate the cloud-based framework by comparing the results of climate analysis with ground truth data and existing datasets. This involves assessing the accuracy and reliability of the methods and algorithms used in the framework.

The goal is to develop interactive visualizations and tools to present the results of climate time series analysis. This includes providing decision support for stakeholders, policymakers, and land managers by generating insights and recommendations based on the analysis outcomes.

The objective is to optimize the performance of the cloud-based framework by exploring parallel computing techniques, data storage strategies, and efficient algorithms to handle large-scale remote sensing datasets and ensure timely analysis.

The research aims to apply the developed framework to real-world case studies, in this case the Rufiji Basin, and demonstrate its effectiveness in analysing climate time series data. This includes exploring potential applications in environmental monitoring, land use planning, climate change impact assessment, and natural resource management.

The objectives mentioned above provide a roadmap for the research to address the challenges associated with climate time series analysis using cloud-based remote sensing techniques. By achieving these objectives, the research aims to contribute to a better understanding of climate dynamics and their interactions for informed decision-making and sustainable resource management.

1.4. Study Area

Location, LULC and Climate

Fig. 1 Rufiji River Basin Catchment

The Rufiji River Basin (see Fig. 1) is the largest river basin in Tanzania and in East Africa. It covers approximately 203,512 km², or 20%, a fifth of the total land area of Tanzania. Its elevation rises from sea level at the Indian Ocean coast to over 3000 meters in the interior of Tanzania (IRA [2014](#)). The Rufiji River basin supplies water for around 4.5 million people and generates 80% of Tanzania's hydropower.

The Rufiji River is approximately 600 km long and has a complex network of tributaries, including the Kilombero, Great Ruaha, and Luwegu rivers. It originates in the Eastern Arc Mountains and drains into the Indian Ocean near the Rufiji Delta. The river has a diverse hydrological regime, with both seasonal and perennial flow patterns influenced by rainfall patterns and catchment characteristics.

The Rufiji River basin is known for its rich biodiversity, the basin encompasses a variety of habitats, including montane forests, savannah woodlands, floodplains, and estuaries, supporting a diverse array of plant and animal species. It is home to several iconic wildlife species, such as elephants, lions, hippos, crocodiles, and a wide range of bird species. The

Selous Game Reserve, a UNESCO World Heritage site, is located in the Rufiji River basin and is one of the largest protected areas in Africa (UNESCO [2023](#)).

The basin provides essential ecosystem services and supports various ecological processes. It regulates water flow, maintains water quality, and provides habitat for aquatic and terrestrial species. The wetlands and floodplains within the basin act as important breeding grounds for fish and support water-dependent wildlife. The mangrove forests in the Rufiji Delta provide protection against coastal erosion, support fish nurseries, and serve as important carbon sinks.

The basin is significant for agricultural activities and supports the livelihoods of local communities. The fertile floodplains and alluvial soils along the river are used for farming, including the cultivation of rice, maize, sugarcane, and cash crops. The basin also supports livestock grazing and provides water for irrigation systems, it also holds substantial water resources that are essential for various sectors. It supports hydropower generation, with the Mtera and Kidatu dams built along the Great Ruaha River. These dams contribute to the national power grid and provide opportunities for irrigation. Water from the Rufiji River is also used for domestic water supply, industrial purposes, and supporting tourism activities.

Unfortunately, the basin faces various conservation challenges. Deforestation, unsustainable agriculture practices, overfishing, and pollution pose threats to the basin's ecosystems and biodiversity. Climate change impacts, such as changes in rainfall patterns and increased frequency of droughts and floods, further affect the basin's hydrology and ecosystems. Sustainable management of water resources, biodiversity conservation, and community engagement are crucial for the long-term sustainability of the Rufiji River basin.

2. STATE OF THE ART: STUDIES, SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGIES

2.1. Remote Sensing and GIS Related Studies

These papers provide a range of perspectives on the Rufiji River Basin, including the performance of climate models in simulating rainfall in the basin and the interdependencies of water, energy, food, and environment sectors in the basin. On the other side, previous studies that utilize Google Earth Engine also provide a guide and reference upon which this research is primarily based.

GEE has demonstrated its emergence as a web-based platform with the capability to efficiently handle extensive satellite data. Moreover, GEE is recognized as a versatile tool with diverse applications across multiple domains of expertise, including earth and planetary sciences, environmental studies, computational science, agriculture, biology, engineering, and more. These attributes have facilitated global researchers in simplifying the creation, reproduction, analysis, and collaborative sharing of algorithms through cloud-based remote sensing applications (Montoya *et al.* [2023](#)).

Koutsouris *et al* 2016 conducted a hydro-climatological study of the Kilombero Valley which is a sub-basin of the Rufiji basin using GPDs. This is relevant because it sheds light to not only a sample region and its climate but provide an in-depth comparison of GPDs, so it's known which data source fits this study with limited in-situ precipitation data. An appropriate GPD largely depends on the purpose for which it is being used as well as required temporal and spatial resolution and scale (Koutsouris *et al* [2016](#)).

Fig. 2 Kilombero sub-basin (Farr *et al.*, 2007),

Evaluation of the performance of regional climate models in simulating rainfall characteristics over the Mbarali River catchment (see Fig. 2) in the Rufiji Basin show a unimodal rainfall regime where the region experienced a single rainy season extending usually between late November-early December to early-mid May (Mutayoba & Kashaigili [2017](#)). This is relevant as it serves as reference later analyse the rainfall pattern in this study to see how it compares.

Numerous river basins in the developing regions of the world are experiencing swift transformation due to both deliberate and unforeseen initiatives by governments, corporations, and local actors. These endeavours are ostensibly aimed at satisfying the rising requirements for agricultural and energy production. However, the decision-making process for investments becomes intricate due to conflicting objectives within these river basins. These conflicting goals may involve increasing the capacity and dependability of hydropower generation, providing water for urban and agricultural expansion, and simultaneously minimizing both costs and environmental impacts (Connor *et al.* [2015](#)).

3. METHODOLOGY AND IMPLEMENTATION

3.1. Flow Process

To begin with, one needs to have an account on GEE, once logged in, the Code Editor, which is the primary interface for writing scripts in JavaScript API to perform geodata analysis becomes accessible. GEE is a platform for earth observation and data analysis that provides access to a large database of satellite imagery and geospatial datasets.

Importing datasets like CHIRPS, MODIS and NASA SMAP into GEE is a straightforward process because these datasets are already hosted on GEE's public data archive. Here's how it typically works together with other tools as per this research depicted in (Fig. 3) while following the steps below.

The NDVI, NDWI, LST, Precipitation and Soil Moisture datasets were imported in the GEE platform by accessing the MCD43A4 v6.1, MOD09GA v6.1, MOD11A2 v6.1, UCSB-CHG/CHIRPS/DAILY and NASA_USDA/HSL/SMAP10KM datasets respectively.

A date filter provided temporal extent set as dates 'from' 'to' within which this study gathered the time series for respective dataset/study parameter from the year 2000 to 2022 and a cloud filter was applied to get cloud-free images for quality.

These datasets were then tailored to fit this study region by incorporating the area of interest geometry derived from delineating the river basin from USGS SRTM DEM in QGIS and producing a shapefile of the watershed boundaries which was then uploaded into GEE as an asset and then imported in the GEE code editor to clip the analysis on the area of interest. The spatial limit is set by defining the area of study, in this case this area was imported as an xml asset file that was pre-loaded and integrated into the GEE.

The NDVI, NDWI and LST values were derived by selecting the "NDVI", "NDWI", and "LST_Day_1km" bands respectively from the MODIS datasets. For LST measurements, the "LST_Day_1km" has a resolution of 1 km was scaled by a factor of 0.02, and to converted to degrees Celsius from Kelvin by subtracting 273.15 from the scaled values (Garai *et al.* [2022](#)). The soil moisture values were derived from the SMAP bands "ssm" and "susm" for surface and sub-surface soil moisture respectively.

GEE provides functions to visualize datasets directly in the Code Editor's map window, therefore running the script displayed thematic maps, charts, and raw data in the GEE IDE. MODIS datasets produced NDVI, NDWI and LST, CHIRPS produced rainfall maps and charts, while the NASA SMAP dataset gave soil moisture maps, charts, numerical data. All data was then exported from GEE to Google Drive and downloaded as raster files in GeoTIFF format and their related numerical data in csv format for analysis in GIS and data analysis software for spatial and statistical analysis respectively.

For further spatial analysis the images were imported and processed in QGIS, and as for statistical analysis the numerical data was imported in a Visual Studio Python environment ,

where it underwent various statistical analysis related to climate science, accuracy assessment and validation. The results were charts and tables which were then saved and included in this report.

Fig. 3 Flow Chart for Climate Multi-temporal Analysis with Google Earth Engine

3.2. Delineation of Catchment Area/River Basin

Watershed delineation from a DEM was performed within the open-source GIS software QGIS. The delineation of river basin catchment areas is a fundamental component of hydrological analysis and is essential for understanding the movement and management of water resources.

DEMs are invaluable in geospatial analysis, particularly in the realm of hydrology. Delineating river basin catchment areas from DEMs is crucial for various applications, such as flood modelling, water resource management, and environmental studies. This report details the process for performing this task within the QGIS software environment, utilizing the GRASS GIS plugin for hydrological analysis.

High-quality DEM data forms the foundation of this analysis. DEM data used in this study was from the SRTM with a spatial resolution of 30 m, downloaded from the Earth Explorer USGS website (USGS [2023](#)). Ensuring compatibility with QGIS, such as using the GeoTIFF format, was critical for a smooth workflow.

The utilization of the GRASS GIS plugin in QGIS was integral in the watershed delineation process. Setting up a GRASS Location matching the extent of the DEM ensures consistency in the analysis. This step is accomplished through the "Processing" menu within the QGIS interface.

Watershed Delineation

By using the "r.watershed" tool provided by GRASS GIS, various critical layers, including flow direction, flow accumulation, and the watershed itself were calculated. The DEM layer was imported and an outlet or pour point set for the calculations. Upon successful execution of the "r.watershed" tool, the resulting layers were visualized and analyzed within the QGIS interface. Key layers examined included the catchment area boundaries, flow direction, and flow accumulation.

The catchment area layer output was converted into a vector polygon shapefile using the "Raster to Vector" tool available in QGIS. The resulting polygon represented the delineated catchment boundaries of the Rufiji River Basin. It was saved and exported as needed ready for further geospatial analysis after it was imported in GEE.

The accuracy and precision of this method are contingent on the quality of the DEM and the appropriate setup of the GRASS Location. The utilization of open-source software and freely available data sources makes this method accessible and cost-effective, benefiting various scientific and environmental disciplines hence this study chose it.

3.3. Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI)

NDVI is used to quantify vegetation greenness and is useful in understanding vegetation density and assessing changes in plant health. NDVI is calculated as a ratio between the red (R) and near infrared (NIR) values (see Eq. 1)(USGS [2023](#)).

$$NDVI = \frac{NIR - Red}{NIR + Red}$$

Eq. 1

Using the MODIS MCD43A4 surface reflectance composites as inputs the NDVI output ranges in value from -1.0 to 1.0

Chlorophyll, a key pigment indicating plant health, readily absorbs visible light, while the internal leaf structure efficiently reflects near-infrared light. In cases where a plant experiences dehydration, illness, or other stress factors, its spongy layer deteriorates, causing the plant to absorb more near-infrared light instead of reflecting it. Consequently, monitoring changes in near-infrared light compared to red light serves as a reliable indicator of chlorophyll presence, which in turn correlates with the overall health of the plant (EOS [2023](#)).

3.4. Normalized Difference Water Index (NDWI)

The NDWI uses two near-IR channels; one centered approximately at 0.86 μm , and the other at 1.24 μm . (see Eq. 2)

$$NDWI = \frac{(\rho(0.86\mu\text{m}) - \rho(1.24\mu\text{m}))}{(\rho(0.86\mu\text{m}) + \rho(1.24\mu\text{m}))}$$

Eq. 2

where $\rho(\lambda)$ is apparent reflectance, and λ is wavelength.

$\rho(\lambda)$ is equal to $\pi L(\lambda)/[\cos(q_0) E_0(\lambda)]$ with $L(\lambda)$, q_0 , and $E_0(\lambda)$ being the measured radiance, the solar zenith angle, and the solar irradiance above the earth atmosphere, respectively. (Gao [1996](#)). The main reason for using NDWI is that near-infrared (NIR) is highly sensitive to the moisture content in soil and vegetation.

Simply put, NDWI is calculated using the near-infrared (NIR – MODIS band 2) and the short-wave infrared (SWIR – MODIS band 6) reflectance. (EC JRC [2011](#)) (See Eq. 3)

$$NDWI = \frac{NIR - SWIR}{NIR + SWIR}$$

Eq. 3

Using the MODIS MOD09GA surface reflectance composites as inputs the resulting index value ranges from -1.0 to 1.0. NDWI is useful for remote sensing vegetation liquid water status from space, the reflectance properties of green vegetation, dry vegetation and soils, and the absorption and scattering properties of atmospheric gases and aerosols.

3.5. Land Surface Temperature (LST)

LST plays a pivotal role in understanding the physical dynamics of land-surface processes at both regional and global levels, encompassing the outcomes of all interactions between the Earth's surface and the atmosphere, as well as the exchange of energy between the two. (Wan [2014](#))

The LST value in the level-2 LST products is retrieved with the generalized split-window algorithm (Wan & Dozier [1996](#)) in Eq. 4 from brightness_temperature values in MODIS bands 31 and 32.

$$LST = b_0 + \left(b_1 + b_2 \frac{1-e}{e} + b_3 \frac{De}{e^2} \right) \frac{T_i + T_j}{2} + \left(b_4 + b_5 \frac{1-e}{e} + b_6 \frac{De}{e^2} \right) \frac{T_i - T_j}{2}$$

Eq. 4

where ϵ and $\Delta\epsilon$ are the mean and difference of the emissivity values in bands 31 and 32, and $i = 31, j = 32$.

The coefficients b_k ($k = 0, 1-6$) depend on viewing zenith angle, atmospheric surface temperature and water vapor. These coefficients were derived from regression analysis of the radiative transfer simulation data for LSTs varying in the range from $T_s\text{-air} - 16$ K to $T_s\text{-air} + 16$ K, where $T_s\text{-air}$ is the surface air temperature (Wan [2014](#)).

The formula was originally derived by (Becker and Li [1990](#)) for retrieving clear-sky LSTs from NOAA-9 data under all surface and atmosphere conditions without considering the viewing zenith angle.

The formula used to estimate LST from MODIS data depends on the specific algorithm or product being used. The Split-Window Algorithm takes advantage of the atmospheric window in the thermal infrared spectrum to estimate LST. It utilizes two thermal infrared bands (typically bands 31 and 32) to correct for atmospheric effects, such as water vapor and aerosol absorption. The radiance values from these bands are used in the formula to calculate LST.

3.6. CHIRPS Precipitation Estimation

The CHIRPS process consists of three primary components CHP_{clim}, the satellite-based CHIRP, and the blending procedure involving station data to create CHIRPS. (Funk *et al.* 2005) as depicted in (see Fig. 4)

Fig. 4 CHIRPS production and application schema (Funk *et al.* 2015)

CHIRPS estimates precipitation by combining satellite observations, ground station data, and statistical techniques. The mathematical formulation of CHIRPS involves several steps. Here is a general overview of the mathematical process:

By using satellite observations of infrared brightness temperature which is related to cloud properties and precipitation. The satellite data is obtained from sensors on board NOAA's GOES, Meteosat, TRMM and GPM that measure the radiation emitted by the Earth's surface in the infrared spectrum.

The satellite data is calibrated to convert brightness temperature values into precipitation estimates. This calibration process involves statistical relationships between brightness temperature and precipitation derived from ground station data measured by rain gauges which provide accurate and localized precipitation information. The ground station data is used for calibration, validation, and quality control purposes.

For regions where ground station data is sparse or unavailable CHIRPS employs spatial interpolation techniques to generate precipitation estimates. Interpolation methods, such as kriging or inverse distance weighting, are used to fill in the gaps between the available ground station measurements. The satellite observations and interpolated ground station data are combined using statistical blending techniques. These techniques aim to optimize the representation of precipitation patterns by assigning appropriate weights to each data source based on their reliability and accuracy (Funk *et al.* 2005).

Ancillary data is also incorporated into the CHIRPS model, such as terrain elevation, land cover, and climate factors, to account for spatial variations in precipitation. These data layers are integrated into the mathematical model to improve the accuracy of the estimates.

CHIRPS applies quality control measures to identify and eliminate erroneous or unreliable data. This involves identifying outliers, checking for inconsistencies, and applying statistical tests to ensure data integrity.

The mathematical model is designed to process and update the data regularly, allowing for near-real-time monitoring of rainfall patterns, therefore the precipitation estimates are produced on a daily basis.

It's important to note that the specific mathematical algorithms used in CHIRPS may be more complex and involve advanced statistical techniques beyond the scope of this general overview. The CHIRPS methodology is continuously refined and updated as new research and data become available, ensuring the accuracy and reliability of the precipitation estimates.

4. DATA, INSTRUMENTS, AND SOFTWARE

Several instruments, tools and software and their associated functionalities and packages they are essential components of research in various fields. They are used to collect, analyse, and interpret data, as well as to facilitate the research process. In this research the various data, their collection instruments and software were used for tasks such as data collection, data analysis, geospatial analysis, coding and programming, cloud computing, version control, documentation, and writing.

4.1. Datasets

4.1.1. SRTM Elevation Data

The SRTM employed interferometry to collect detailed elevation data of the Earth's terrain. This method involves capturing two separate images of the same region from distinct perspectives. The minor discrepancies between these dual images enable researchers to calculate the elevation of the land. When two sets of radar data, acquired interferometrically, are overlaid, the initial output generated is known as an interferogram, which can be used to create detailed elevation models.

The NASADEM datasets are crafted from the original SRTM telemetry. The LP DAAC oversees the preservation and dissemination of the NASA MEaSUREs DEM version 1 dataset, known as NASADEM_SIM. This dataset offers a comprehensive global image mosaic derived from the SRTM at a detailed resolution of 1 arc second (NASA JPL [2020](#)).

To enhance the precision of the surface elevation data, NASADEM has integrated data from the Terra satellite's ASTER GDEM Version 2 and used ground control points from the ICESat GLAS. These improvements not only augmented the geolocation accuracy but also involved converting elevation measurements to a geoid reference. Additionally, the datasets include enhancements such as using GDEMs and the PRISM AW3D30 DEM, along with sophisticated interpolation techniques to fill in any data gaps (NASA JPL [2020](#)).

The NASADEM data are available in segments of 1 degree by 1 degree latitude and longitude, encompassing all terrestrial regions from 60° N to 56° S latitude. This coverage includes approximately 80% of the Earth's land surface (NASA JPL [2020](#)).

The processed SRTM radar data can be tailored to meet the needs of the military, civil, and scientific user communities. But other uses of this data include improved water drainage modelling which is essentially what this research does for the Rufiji River Basin, more realistic flight simulators, navigation safety, better locations for cell phone towers, and even improved maps for backpackers. Just about any project that requires accurate knowledge of the shape and height of the land can benefit from this data. Some examples are flood control, soil conservation, reforestation, volcano monitoring, earthquake research, and glacier movement monitoring.

4.1.2. NDVI-Dataset

The MCD43A4 Version 6.1 dataset from the MODIS provides daily BRDF-NBAR output. This dataset synthesizes 16 days' worth of data, hence a 16 days temporal resolution, from both the Terra and Aqua MODIS instruments and presents it at a spatial resolution of 500 m. By accounting for and eliminating the variations in reflectance caused by different sensor view angles, the dataset ensures that the resulting NBAR product is both stable and uniform (Schaaf [2023](#)).

The MODIS datasets have been widely utilized for vegetation monitoring on a large scale, primarily because they are accessible at no cost and offer a relatively high frequency of data capture (Pettorelli *et al.* [2005](#)), this high temporal resolution significantly enhances the ability to observe changes in vegetation over time. The product is designed to provide consistent and reliable measurements of vegetation at a global scale.

For the purposes of this study, the capabilities of GEE were leveraged, a powerful cloud-based platform for Earth observation data analysis, to extract the NDVI specifically for the region of Rufiji River Basin. This research focused on data spanning from 2000 to 2022. This approach allowed us to streamline the analysis of vegetation dynamics and health within this specific time frame and geographical area, providing valuable insights into temporal trends and potential environmental changes.

4.1.3. NDWI-Dataset

The MOD09GA Version 6.1 product delivers an approximation of the spectral reflectance for the Earth's surface as captured by the first seven bands of the Terra satellite's MODIS. These reflectance estimates have been adjusted to correct for atmospheric interferences such as gases, aerosol particles, and Rayleigh scattering. In addition to the primary data offering surface reflectance at a 500-meter resolution, this product also includes observation details and quality indicators. Complementing these are an additional ten bands of observations and corresponding geolocation flags at a coarser resolution of 1 kilometre. The reflectance data provided by the MOD09GA serves as foundational input for a multitude of land-focused MODIS products (Vermote [2023](#)).

By employing the dataset MOD09GA version 6.1 product, developed by NASA's MODIS land product team, researchers can access NDWI measurements with a 500-meter spatial resolution that are updated daily. This level of detail and update frequency is vital for tracking and responding to environmental changes over time. The NDWI data, freely available and with a high temporal resolution, is especially valuable for large-scale hydrological studies, including irrigation monitoring, drought assessment, and flood risk evaluation.

In the case of analysing water content in The Rufiji River Basin, platforms such as GEE offer significant computational power, enabling the processing of large datasets like NDWI. Through GEE obtained NDWI data for specific time intervals across multiple years. This facilitated a longitudinal analysis, allowing for the observation of patterns, trends, and potentially anomalous conditions related to water content in the environment from 2000 to 2022.

4.1.4. LST-Dataset

The Version 6.1 of the MOD11A2 product offers a per-pixel average of LST and emissivity data over an 8-day span, with each pixel having a 1-kilometer spatial resolution on a grid measuring 1,200 km by 1,200 km. The values for each pixel within the MOD11A2 dataset are derived by averaging the LST values from all the corresponding pixels in the daily MOD11A1 product over the same 8-day window. This specific 8-day interval is strategic because it is half the duration of the exact repeat cycle for the orbital paths of the Terra and Aqua satellites. Accompanying the primary data of daytime and night-time surface temperatures are several supplementary layers, including quality assurance metrics, timestamps of observations, angles of the satellite's zenith view, and the percentage of the time when the sky is clear. Additionally, emissivity values for bands 31 and 32, which correspond to different land cover types, are also provided (Wan [2023](#)). This study only used the daytime LST “LST_Day_1km”.

4.1.5. Climate Hazards Group InfraRed Precipitation with Station data (CHIRPS) Dataset

Precipitation data plays a crucial role in most hydroclimatological investigations. However, in numerous parts of the world, the available records of observed precipitation are often limited, inconsistent, and may have discrepancies. This challenge is particularly prominent in various regions of Eastern Africa (Sawunyama and Hughes, [2008](#)). Consequently, efforts have been made to generate GPDs by utilizing satellite, reanalysis, and/or interpolated observed data sources (Huffman *et al.* [2007](#), Dee *et al.* [2011](#), and Harris *et al.* [2014](#)). The advantage of GPDs lies in their ability to fill in both temporal and spatial data gaps, which can potentially enhance the ability to comprehend the dynamics of the water cycle (Koutsouris *et al.* [2015](#)).

The CHIRPS dataset, developed by the Climate Hazards group, enhances existing methods for intelligent interpolation techniques and provides high-resolution, long-term precipitation estimates based on infrared CCD observations. The approach includes the following key components: It is founded on a 0.05° climatology that utilizes satellite data to represent regions with limited gauge data. It incorporates daily, pentadal, and monthly precipitation estimates based on CCD data from 1981 to the present at a 0.05° resolution.

It combines station data to produce an initial dataset with an approximate 2-day delay and a final dataset with an average delay of about 3 weeks. It employs a unique blending process that considers the spatial correlation structure of CCD estimates to determine interpolation weights (Funk *et al.* [2015](#)).

CHIRPS was created in collaboration with scientists at the USGS EROS Centre to deliver reliable, up to date, and more complete datasets for several early warning objectives. Spanning 50°S-50°N (and all longitudes), starting in 1981 to Feb 2016, CHIRPS incorporates 0.05° resolution satellite imagery with in-situ station data to create gridded rainfall time series for trend analysis and seasonal drought monitoring.

The GEE – CHIRPS precipitation tool can be modified to output a time-series of precipitation for a user-defined region. This user-defined region can whether be defined through use of the geometry tool or selected from a specific country. The region is imported into the map through geometry, location name or shapefile.

CHIRPS is a precipitation dataset that combines satellite imagery with ground-based precipitation observations to provide high-quality, gridded rainfall data at global scales. The CHIRPS dataset is derived from the TRMM and the GPCC rain gauge network.

4.1.6. Soil Moisture Dataset

NASA-USDA Enhanced SMAP Global Soil Moisture Data

The NASA-USDA Global soil moisture dataset offers global soil moisture information at a spatial resolution of 0.25°x0.25°. This dataset encompasses various types of soil moisture data, including surface and subsurface moisture in millimetres (mm), soil moisture profiles in percentage (%), and surface and subsurface soil moisture anomalies. To create this dataset, satellite-derived soil moisture observations from SMAP and SMOS are integrated into a modified two-layer Palmer model using the EnKF data assimilation approach. The incorporation of satellite-derived soil moisture observations has significantly enhanced the accuracy of model-based soil moisture predictions, particularly in regions of the world with limited access to reliable precipitation data (NASA [2023](#)).

This data for surface and subsurface soil moisture is only available from April 2015 to August 2022 and superseded by:

SMAP L4 Global 3-hourly 9 km EASE-Grid Surface and Root Zone Soil Moisture

The SMAP Level-4 (L4) Soil Moisture product encompasses surface soil moisture (averaged vertically from 0 to 5 cm), root-zone soil moisture (averaged vertically from 0 to 100 cm), and supplementary research data (not subject to validation). These additional research components comprise surface meteorological forcing variables, soil temperature, evapotranspiration, and net radiation. SMAP L4 ensures a continuous stream of soil moisture information. In instances when the SMAP instrument experiences interruptions, the SMAP L4 soil moisture data relies solely on land model simulations and does not incorporate simultaneous assimilation of SMAP brightness temperature observations (NSIDC [2023](#)).

4.1.7. Ancillary Data

Ancillary data, in the context of various fields such as remote sensing, GIS (Geographic Information Systems), and scientific research, refers to supplementary or supporting information that is not the primary dataset but is essential for interpreting, analysing, or enhancing the understanding of the main data. Ancillary data provides context and additional details that can be critical for the successful utilization of the primary data. The following data sets are later used for validation and accuracy assessment of the CHIRPS as the primary rainfall data.

TRMM: The Tropical Rainfall Measuring Mission generates precipitation approximations by integrating microwave and infrared satellite precipitation estimates. This integration allows the product to be recalibrated to monthly rain gauge scales. TRMM's temporal coverage spans from January 1998 to 2015, with a daily temporal resolution. The spatial coverage of the estimates extends from 180°W to 180°E and 50°S to 50°N, with a spatial resolution of 0.25° in both latitude and longitude (NASA [2023](#)).

CMAP: The Climate Prediction Centre's Merged Analysis of Precipitation is a global precipitation analysis that combines rain gauge data with precipitation estimates derived from infrared and microwave satellite algorithms. It provides data in five-day (pentad) and monthly intervals. The temporal coverage of CMAP spans from January 1979 to the present, and it offers a spatial resolution of 2.5° in both latitude and longitude (NOAA [2023](#)).

CMORPH: The Climate Prediction Centre Morphing Technique is a high-resolution precipitation analysis method that utilizes microwave observations from low-orbiting satellites. The movement of these features is determined using spatial propagation information derived from infrared data from geostationary satellites. CMORPH has been operational since December 7, 2002, and continues to the present. It provides data at three-hourly and daily intervals, covering a spatial domain from 0°E to 360°E (encompassing the entire globe in longitude) and from 60°S to 60°N. The data, which is updated daily, has a spatial resolution of 0.25° in both latitude and longitude (NOAA [2023](#)).

TMA: Tanzania Meteorological Association is the designated National Meteorological Authority of Tanzania that provides and regulates weather and climate services (TMA [2023](#)). TMA's weather data is useful to validate other data sources (MODIS LST here) a procedure which is significant in enhancing the accuracy and reliability of satellite-based weather measurements. It has ground weather stations that fall within the region of study, from these, 4 reference stations were chose.

4.2. Instruments

Satellite instruments dedicated to Earth observation are pivotal in providing critical data about the planet's surface, atmosphere, and oceans. These sophisticated tools, orbiting Earth aboard satellites, capture a wide range of information, from temperature and humidity profiles to land and sea surface patterns. They employ various technologies like multispectral imaging, radar, and lidar to monitor environmental changes, track weather patterns, and study ecological systems. These instruments play a vital role in climate research, natural disaster monitoring, and resource management by offering high-resolution, continuous, and global coverage that is not feasible from ground-based observations alone. The data they provide is invaluable for scientific research, policy-making, and in addressing global challenges such as climate change, deforestation, and ocean health.

4.2.1. Space Shuttle Radar Topography Mission (SRTM)

SRTM a project spearheaded by NASA in collaboration with the NGA and supported by the DLR and ASI, German, and Italian space agencies respectively. The SRTM's core mission was to create a detailed DEM of the Earth by utilizing radar interferometry. This technology was a crucial part of the payload aboard the space shuttle Endeavour on the STS-99 mission, which was launched on February 11, 2000, and orbited for 11 days (NASA JPL [2020](#)).

The SRTM was divided into three main components as shown in (Fig. 5). The primary antenna (TX/RX) that emitted the radar signal and was equipped with special panels designed to capture the radar pulse that returned after reflecting from the Earth's surface, this was housed within the Space Shuttle Endeavour's payload bay, to which a mast was affixed.

The mast extended outwards and was capped with an outboard (RX/receiving) antenna at its extremity. Upon reaching orbit, the mast was unfolded from a storage container linked to the antenna's supporting structure, extending a distance of 60 meters into space.

The outboard (RX/receiving) antenna positioned at the tip of this mast served as the secondary point of reception for the radar signals, completing the necessary setup for capturing the two separate images required for interferometric analysis.

Fig. 5 SRTM space segment. Shown are the main components of both the X- and the C-band SAR system. TX: transmitter, RX: receiver. (Bernhard et al. [2003](#))

4.2.2. The Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer (MODIS)

The MODIS is an instrument onboard two NASA satellites: Terra and Aqua. It is designed to capture high-resolution data and images of the Earth's surface and atmosphere. MODIS provides valuable information for a wide range of applications, including climate research, land cover mapping, vegetation monitoring, and disaster management.

MODIS serves as a critical instrument on board the Terra (formerly known as EOS AM-1) and Aqua (formerly known as EOS PM-1) satellites. Terra follows an orbital path around the Earth that takes it from north to south across the equator during the morning, while Aqua follows a trajectory from south to north over the equator in the afternoon (NASA [2023](#)).

MODIS consistently acquires data in 36 spectral channels, covering the entire globe every 1 to 2 days. Its wide spectral range makes MODIS data valuable for a variety of research fields, including the assessment of vegetation health, tracking changes in land cover and land use, monitoring oceans and ocean biology, sea surface temperature analysis, and cloud observation. Additionally, it plays a crucial role in the surveillance of wildfires, natural disasters, and oil spills. Notably, MODIS data products are accessible in real-time and near real-time. Raw MODIS data is received in real-time through direct broadcast stations worldwide, directly from the satellite. NASA's LANCE offers several MODIS products within three hours of satellite observation (NASA [2023](#)).

Fig. 6 Terra spacecraft and its instruments/sensors. (NASA)

Data collection by Terra commenced in the early months of 2000. The spacecraft is equipped with five instruments ASTER, CERES, MISR, MODIS and MOPITT, contributed by NASA and its global partners(Fig. 6).

Fig. 7 Aqua Satellite and its instruments/sensors (NASA)

Aqua is equipped with six cutting-edge instruments orbiting at a near-polar low-Earth orbit. These instruments include the AIRS, the AMSU-A, the HSB, the AMSR-E, the MODIS, and the CERES (Fig. 7). Each instrument possesses distinct features and capabilities, and when combined, they create a formidable suite for monitoring and studying Earth (NASA AQUA [2023](#)).

MODIS captures data in various spectral bands, allowing for the retrieval of multiple geophysical parameters such as land surface temperature, vegetation indices, cloud properties, sea surface temperature, and atmospheric profiles. The captured data is processed and distributed as standard products, including surface reflectance, vegetation indices, land surface temperature, cloud mask, and many others. MODIS data is freely available to the public through NASA's EOSDIS.

4.2.3. Soil Moisture Active Passive (SMAP)

The SMAP mission is a satellite project that captures global measurements of surface soil moisture. Launched in January 2015, the SMAP satellite is outfitted with a duo of instruments: an active radar and a passive radiometer, designed to work in tandem for the global measurement of soil moisture and the freeze/thaw status of the Earth's land surfaces. Both instruments utilize a shared feed horn and a rotating reflector, which is angled away from the direct-downward position (nadir) and spins around the nadir axis at a rate of 14.6 revolutions per minute. This setup enables a scanning antenna beam that consistently hits the Earth's surface at a 40-degree angle. The antenna, with a span of 6 meters and a weight of 65.5 kilograms features a gold-coated mesh construction. This mesh not only transmits radar signals but also captures the returning echoes and gathers microwave emissions for the radiometer to measure soil moisture (Fig. 8) (NASA JPL [2023](#)).

Fig. 8 SMAP Spacecraft and its instruments/sensors (NASA)

Originally, the mission sought to leverage the strengths of both radar (which provides high-resolution imagery but is less sensitive to soil moisture) and radiometer (which offers high accuracy in moisture detection but at a lower spatial resolution data (NASA JPL [2023](#)).

The SMAP instruments include an L-band radar with three polarization options (vertical-vertical (VV), horizontal-horizontal (HH), and horizontal-vertical (HV)) and an L-band radiometer capable of measuring different polarizations, including the third and fourth Stokes parameters. The choice of L-band frequency is deliberate, allowing the detection of soil moisture beneath moderate vegetation cover and regardless of weather conditions or time of day. The various polarizations are key to making precise soil moisture calculations while accounting for factors such as vegetation density, surface texture, Faraday rotation, and other environmental influences (NASA JPL [2023](#)).

The combined processing of radar and radiometer data was intended to yield soil moisture information at a detailed 10 km resolution and freeze/thaw states at an even finer 3 km resolution, satisfying the mission's scientific objectives. The consistency of the antenna's incidence angle across the wide 1000-km swath simplifies data analysis and supports the precise estimation of soil moisture and freeze/thaw conditions. The integration of radiometer data (providing high accuracy at 40 km resolution) with radar data (offering higher resolution at 3 km but with less moisture accuracy) was planned to produce high-fidelity soil moisture maps at a 10 km resolution. However, after the radar's malfunction in July 2015, SMAP's radar data has been supplemented with data from the European Union's Copernicus Sentinel-1 C-band radar to continue the mission's objectives (NASA JPL [2023](#)).

4.3. Software

Software for geospatial data analysis is designed to capture, store, manipulate, analyse, manage, and present all types of geographical data. These sophisticated tools enable researchers and professionals to visualize trends, patterns, and relationships in geospatial data.

4.3.1. Google Earth Engine (GEE)

Google Earth Engine is a cloud-based platform that provides access to a vast archive of geospatial data and powerful computational tools for analysing and visualizing the Earth's environment at scale. It combines satellite imagery, remote sensing data, and geospatial data from various sources to enable scientists, researchers, and developers to perform advanced geospatial analysis and generate actionable insights (Noel [2017](#)).

Fig. 9 GEE Simplified System Architecture (Noel et al. [2017](#))

Components of GEE as depicted in its system architecture (see Fig. 9). The following is a breakdown of each part as indicated in the diagram:

Earth Engine Code Editor: This is likely a specialized integrated development environment (IDE) for writing and executing scripts that interact with Earth observation data, such as satellite imagery and geospatial datasets.

Client Libraries (JavaScript / Python): These are programming libraries provided for the client side, which developers can use to interact with the Earth Engine system using JavaScript or Python. These libraries would facilitate the building of applications by providing predefined classes and functions.

Third-party Web Apps: This section refers to applications developed by external parties (not the maintainers of the Earth Engine system) that use the Earth Engine's APIs and data to provide additional functionalities or custom user experiences.

Web REST APIs: Representational State Transfer (REST) APIs are web services that allow for interacting with the Earth Engine system over HTTP, enabling users to perform operations like querying data, submitting processing jobs, and retrieving results.

On-the-fly Computation:

Front Ends: User interfaces or service endpoints that users interact with directly, such as web pages or API gateways.

- **Compute Masters:** Servers that manage the distribution and coordination of computation tasks across multiple compute servers.
- **Compute Servers:** The actual servers where data processing tasks are executed.
- **Caches:** Storage systems used to temporarily hold data to speed up data retrieval and reduce processing time for frequently accessed information.

Batch Computation: Systems designed for processing large volumes of data where the data is collected over time and processed as a batch, as opposed to on-the-fly computations that are typically executed immediately upon request.

Data Stores:

- **Fusion Tables:** A now-deprecated Google service for data management. Fusion Tables allowed users to store, share, query, and visualize data tables; in this context, it probably refers to a similar system for managing tabular geospatial data.
- **Tilestore Servers:** Servers dedicated to storing and serving tiled data, such as map tiles used in web mapping applications.
- **Asset Database:** A database for storing assets, which in the context of Earth Engine, could be various types of geospatial data or metadata.

This is a high-level overview and each component can be quite complex in its own right, involving intricate engineering and specialized knowledge of geospatial data and distributed computing.

Earth Engine offers a comprehensive data catalog with petabytes of geospatial data, including satellite imagery from various sensors (e.g., Landsat, MODIS, Sentinel), climate and weather data, elevation data, land cover data, and more. The catalog continues to expand with new data being added regularly. Earth Engine provides an integrated code editor that supports JavaScript and Python scripting for data analysis and visualization. The code editor offers a collaborative environment with features like syntax highlighting, auto-completion, and a console for interactive experimentation. GEE offers APIs in JavaScript and Python, allowing developers to access Earth Engine's capabilities programmatically. The APIs provide functions and methods for querying data, applying geospatial operations, and visualizing results. Earth Engine provides a wide range of geospatial analysis capabilities, including spatial and temporal filtering, image compositing, spectral indices computation (e.g., NDVI, NDWI), pixel-level and feature-level operations, data fusion, time series analysis, and machine learning algorithms. Earth Engine offers tools for visualizing geospatial data, including interactive

maps, time series charts, histograms, and other visualization techniques. It supports both 2D and 3D visualization, allowing you to explore data from different perspectives. GEE leverages the power of cloud computing to perform large-scale geospatial analysis efficiently. It utilizes distributed computing and parallel processing to handle massive datasets and complex calculations. Earth Engine supports collaboration and knowledge sharing among users. You can share code scripts, datasets, and visualizations with others, collaborate on projects, and access a vibrant community of users and experts.

Fig. 10 Google Earth Engine Code Editor/IDE (GEE 2023)

The screenshot (see Fig. 10) of the GEE interface with various parts labelled. Here's an explanation of the labelled parts based on standard GEE layout:

Script Editor: This is where the JavaScript code is written and edited. It allows the user to create, modify, and execute scripts for analysing and visualizing geospatial data.

Console: The console displays outputs from the code, such as print statements, error messages, and the results of computations. In this screenshot, it shows an error message related to the `.clip()` function, indicating a problem with the code execution.

Inspector: This tool is used to click on the map and inspect the values of the pixels or features at the selected location. It provides detailed information about the data layers present at the point of interest.

Map View: This shows the spatial data layers. It allows the user to visualize the results of the code execution on the map. In this screenshot, it displays a global view not zoomed into a specific region.

Tasks: The Tasks panel is where long-running processes such as data exports are managed. It shows the status of these tasks, like whether they are running, completed, or if there was an error.

Asset Manager: This section of the interface is used to manage the user's personal data assets in GEE, such as uploaded shapefiles, raster data, or saved scripts.

4.3.2. Google Earth Engine REST API

The Earth Engine REST API is a programming interface provided by GEE that allows developers to interact with Earth Engine's geospatial data and analysis capabilities. With the REST API, you can programmatically query, retrieve, and process Earth Engine data using HTTP requests.

The API uses OAuth 2.0 for authentication, allowing you to securely authenticate and authorize requests on behalf of a user or a service account. You can access a wide range of geospatial data, including satellite imagery, terrain data, climate datasets, and more. The API supports querying and retrieving data based on spatial, temporal, and attribute filters and various image processing operations can be applied, such as filtering, image compositing, image transformations, and mathematical operations, to process and analyse Earth Engine images. The API supports geospatial analysis operations, including pixel-based computations, raster algebra, feature-based operations, and spatial aggregations. Processed data or analysis results can be exported in various formats, such as GeoTIFF, CSV, JSON, or visualize them on maps. The API allows batch processing by submitting tasks that run asynchronously and return results once completed. Tasks can include complex analyses or long-running operations. The assets and collections can also be managed, including uploading, updating, and deleting data assets and organizing them into collections.

The Earth Engine REST API documentation provides detailed information on endpoints, request parameters, and response structures. It also includes examples and code snippets to help you get started with using the API (Google Dev [2023](#)).

4.3.3. Quantum GIS (QGIS)

QGIS is a free and open-source GIS software that allows users to view, analyse, and edit geospatial data. It provides a comprehensive set of tools and features for working with maps, spatial data, and conducting geospatial analysis (QGIS [2023](#)).

QGIS allows users to load and display various types of geospatial data, including vector data (points, lines, polygons), raster data (imagery, digital elevation models), and tabular data. It provides tools for editing and digitizing spatial data, such as creating and modifying features, splitting, and merging geometries, and attribute editing. QGIS supports a wide range of data formats, including popular ones like shapefiles, GeoTIFF, KML, and WMS/WFS services. It can also connect to databases like PostgreSQL and MySQL, allowing users to directly interact with spatial databases. QGIS offers a variety of geoprocessing and analysis tools for spatial

operations, including buffer, clip, dissolve, spatial join, and more. It supports spatial querying, overlay analysis, network analysis, interpolation, and other advanced analysis techniques. QGIS provides tools for designing and customizing maps, allowing users to create visually appealing cartographic outputs. It offers options for symbolizing and labelling features, creating legends, adding scale bars, north arrows, and other map elements. Users can also generate print layouts for creating high-quality map compositions. QGIS supports a plugin architecture that allows users to extend its functionality by installing additional plugins. There is a wide range of plugins available, offering additional tools and features for specific tasks or workflows, such as data processing, analysis algorithms, and integration with other software. QGIS supports 3D visualization, allowing users to display and explore spatial data in a three-dimensional environment. It provides options for draping raster and vector data over elevation models and supports navigation and exploration in the 3D view. QGIS has a large and active user community, which contributes to its development, provides support, and shares knowledge. Documentation, tutorials, and forums are available to help users get started, learn new techniques, and troubleshoot issues.

4.3.4. Visual Studio

To perform data analysis with Python in Visual Studio environment, tools, and libraries such as Pandas, NumPy, SciPy and Matplotlib available within Visual Studio or extensions that enhance its capabilities were used.

Visual Studio provides a versatile and powerful environment for Python data analysis, and with the right configuration and libraries, can conduct a wide range of data analysis tasks efficiently. Additionally, other alternative IDEs are like Jupyter Notebook or specialized data science platforms like JupyterLab or Anaconda alongside Visual Studio for data analysis and exploration.

4.3.5. GitHub

GitHub is a web-based platform that provides hosting for version control using Git. It is commonly used to store and manage code repositories, allowing for collaboration among developers. Here's a breakdown of its key features used by this study and how they work:

-Version Control

Integrating GitHub with Visual Studio for version control significantly enhances the efficiency and management of software development projects. GitHub, a widely-used platform for hosting code, facilitates collaborative development and version tracking. When integrated with Visual Studio, a powerful IDE, developers gain a seamless experience for coding and version control within a single environment. This integration allows for easy cloning of repositories, committing changes, and pushing updates back to GitHub directly from Visual Studio. It streamlines the process of branching, merging, and managing pull requests, making collaborative coding more accessible and efficient. Developers can effortlessly track changes, revert to previous versions, and manage different development branches without leaving the Visual Studio interface. This integration fosters a more organized and synchronized workflow,

reducing the likelihood of conflicts and errors that often occur in team projects. Overall, the combination of GitHub and Visual Studio creates a robust platform for developing, maintaining, and deploying software, ensuring code integrity, and facilitating team collaboration.

-Public Repository

Using GitHub as a public repository offers numerous benefits, particularly for open-source projects and collaborative development. As a public platform, GitHub allows developers to share their code with a global community, fostering transparency and collective innovation. It serves as a showcase for individual and organizational projects, allowing developers to demonstrate their skills, share their work, and contribute to others' projects. Public repositories on GitHub enable free access to a vast array of resources, from simple scripts to complex applications, encouraging learning and reuse of code. The platform's in-built features like issue tracking, wikis, and README files enhance project documentation and user engagement. Collaborative features such as forks, pull requests, and merges facilitate community contributions to a project, allowing for continuous improvement and development through collective expertise. Additionally, for projects seeking broader visibility and community engagement, GitHub's public repositories provide an ideal stage for open-source development, attracting potential contributors, users, and even sponsors.

-Web Hosting

Utilizing GitHub as a host for a website (WebGIS) is a strategic and cost-effective choice, especially for developers aiming to showcase geospatial applications and projects. GitHub offers reliable hosting through GitHub Pages, allowing developers to deploy WebGIS applications directly from their repositories. This approach streamlines the process of showcasing and sharing interactive maps and spatial analysis tools with a wider audience. GitHub's robust version control system ensures smooth management of code changes and updates to the WebGIS, facilitating continuous integration and deployment. Moreover, GitHub's support for various web technologies and frameworks makes it a versatile platform for hosting diverse WebGIS applications, whether they are built using simple HTML and JavaScript or more complex frameworks. The platform's inherent collaboration features also promote community involvement, allowing other developers to contribute to the project, report issues, or suggest improvements. By hosting a WebGIS on GitHub, developers not only leverage a reliable and accessible platform but also join a vibrant community where they can gain visibility, feedback, and potential collaborations.

5. RESULTS

5.1. Time Series Analysis

Climatological time series analysis involves the study of climate data over a period of time to identify trends, patterns, and anomalies. It's a fundamental approach in understanding past climate behaviour and making predictions about future climate scenarios. Here's a step-by-step breakdown of how climatological time series analysis is typically conducted: data collection, data processing, time series decomposition, trend analysis, seasonal analysis, anomaly detection, correlation and regression analysis, spectral analysis, statistical forecasting, climate modelling, visualization, reporting, and decision making.

5.1.1. NDVI Time Series

The region was imported into the map. Following this region selection, the MODIS NDVI image collections were imported into GEE to provide a map and time series data for short-term (1 year) average NDVI (Fig. 11) and long-term average NDVI (Fig. 13)

Seasonal/Monthly NDVI

The region undergoes a seasonal cycle of vegetation growth and decline over the course of a year hence a vivid annual vegetation cycle is observed. (Fig. 11 & Fig. 13)

Fig. 11 NDVI Variation in a Year

Fig. 12 NDVI Maximum happens in March (left) and Minimum in October (right)

Interpretation of NDVI Values: NDVI values range from -1 to +1, with higher values indicating healthier and denser vegetation. Values close to +1 represent lush, vigorously growing vegetation, while values closer to -1 indicate non-vegetated surfaces such as water bodies or barren land. Values around 0 typically represent urban areas or sparsely vegetated regions.

A maximum average NDVI value of 0.71 in March indicates a peak in vegetation greenness and health during this month (see Fig. 11). This is typically associated with the onset of the growing season or springtime when temperatures rise, and plants become more active.

A minimum average NDVI value of 0.34 in October suggests a reduction in vegetation greenness and health (see Fig. 11). This is often associated with the end of the growing season or autumn when temperatures start to decrease, and vegetation enters a period of senescence and decline.

The variations in NDVI throughout the year are influenced by several meteorological and environmental factors, including temperature, precipitation, sunlight, and soil moisture. These factors collectively affect plant growth and the health of vegetation. The observed NDVI fluctuations have ecological significance as it impacts ecosystems, agriculture, and water resources. For example, a higher NDVI in March may indicate favourable conditions for crop planting, while a lower NDVI in October might signal the need for harvest or reduced agricultural productivity.

Long-term NDVI

The displayed graph (Fig. 13) shows a time series of NDVI values ranging from approximately 0.3 to 0.7, over a period of 2000 to 2022, indicating moderate to high vegetation health and density. The recurring peaks and troughs suggest a strong seasonal pattern in vegetation cover due to environmental factors such as wet and dry seasons and to a lesser extent agricultural practices like sowing and harvesting. Although there is noticeable interannual variability in the amplitude of the NDVI values, which is attributed to yearly climatic fluctuations, the data does not immediately suggest a significant long-term change in vegetation health during the observed period.

The consistent range of NDVI values suggests that there is no drastic long-term change in vegetation health over the years shown in the graph and the average NDVI maps between year 2000 and 2022)(Fig. 14).

Fig. 13 NDVI Time Series 2000-2022

Fig. 14 NDVI for Year 2000 (left) and NDVI for Year 2022 (right)

5.1.2. NDWI Time Series

After selecting the particular region of interest, the MODIS NDWI image collections were brought into GEE to generate both a map and a time series dataset for the average NDWI over a short period (1 year) (Fig. 15) and a long-term average NDWI spanning 22 years (Fig. 17).

Seasonal/Monthly NDWI

NDWI values typically range from -1 to +1. Higher positive values indicate a higher proportion of water, such as rivers, lakes, or wetlands. Values close to zero or negative values often represent non-water surfaces, such as bare land or urban areas. The region undergoes a seasonal cycle of water availability and dynamics over the course of a year presenting an annual hydrological cycle (see Fig. 15).

Fig. 15 Monthly Average NDWI Variation

Fig. 16 NDWI Maximum happens in February (left) and Minimum in October (right)

A maximum average NDWI value of 0.09 in February indicates a peak in water presence or water abundance during this month (Fig. 15 & Fig. 16). This is associated with factors such as increased rainfall and higher water levels in rivers and lakes.

A minimum average NDWI value of -0.03 in October suggests a reduction in water presence or abundance (Fig. 15 & Fig. Fig. 16). This is associated with factors like decreased rainfall the peak of dry season.

NDWI variations throughout the year reflect changes in the water cycle and are influenced by meteorological factors, including precipitation, temperature, and evaporation. These factors collectively affect water availability and dynamics. The observed NDWI fluctuations have hydrological and environmental significance.

Long term NDWI

The consistent range of NDVI values suggests that there is no drastic long-term change in water abundance over the years (Fig. 17). However, in the average NDWI maps between year 2000 and 2022 (Fig. 18) 2022 shows an increased water content which is directly correlated to increased positive rainfall anomaly in 2022 (Fig. 31).

Fig. 17 NDWI Time Series 2000-2022

Fig. 18 NDWI for Year 2000 (left) and for Year 2022 (right)

5.1.3. Land Surface Temperature Time Series

Together with the region of interest, the MODIS LST image collections were imported into GEE to provide a map and time series data for short-term (1 year) monthly average LST and long-term (22 years) average LST.

Monthly Average Temperature Variation

The temperature observation through the year shows a seasonal temperature variation (Fig. 19 & Fig. 22). During the month of October, the region experiences 37.5°C, its highest temperatures for the year (Fig. 20). This temperature maximum can be attributed to several meteorological factors. In October, the region experiences a favourable angle of solar radiation, with the sun's rays more directly overhead. This results in increased solar heating and higher temperatures. Seasonal changes in atmospheric circulation patterns also contribute to higher temperatures in October. For instance, the region may be under the influence of warm and dry air masses.

Fig. 19 Monthly Average Temperature

Fig. 20 Average Monthly Temperature from 2000-2022 data

Fig. 21 Temperature Minimum happens in April (left) and Maximum in October (right)

Conversely, the month of April marks the period of the lowest temperatures for the year at 26.5°C (Fig. 20). Several meteorological factors can explain this temperature minimum. In April, the region receives reduced solar insolation due to factors such as a lower sun angle and slightly shorter daylight hours, this leads to cooler temperatures.

The observed temperature variations are a consequence of the changing seasons in the region. This annual cycle, with a temperature maximum in October and a minimum in April, is a fundamental aspect of the region's climate.

Long-term Temperature

The region experiences a 22-year average temperature of 30.3°C and during this period 2000-2022, the hottest year was 2003 at 31.5°C and the coolest was 2022 at 28.7°C (Fig. 23) this is further emphasized by the temperature anomalies observation (Fig. 24).

Fig. 22 Temperature Time Series 2000-2022

Fig. 23 Yearly Mean Temperature Series

Temperature Anomaly

The displayed bar chart (Fig. 24) visualizes the deviation of annual average temperatures from a long-term average across a 22-year span. Each bar represents a year, with red bars indicating years where temperatures were above the average (positive anomalies) and blue bars for years below the average (negative anomalies). The chart reveals fluctuations in temperature, with the variance in bar heights reflecting the annual volatility of temperature anomalies. Notably, bars that are significantly taller or shorter than others mark years with extreme temperature deviations, which could signify notable weather events or shifts in climate patterns.

During 2000 to 2022 the maximum positive temperature anomaly was in 2003 at +1.8°C and the maximum negative temperature anomaly was in 2022 at -1.6°C, also there was a 5-year hotter than average temperature from 2009 to 2013 and cooler than average conditions from 2018 to 2022.

Fig. 24 Temperature Anomalies (2000-2022)

Fig. 25 Land Surface Temperature for Year 2000 (left) and Year 2022 (right)

Comparing the spatial distribution of temperature from the beginning to the final year of this study shows a decreased intensity and spread of temperature represented by a spectrum from blue (cool temperature) to red (hot temperature) (Fig. 25).

5.1.4. Rainfall Time Series

The CHIRPS data was brought into GEE to generate time series information for both the short-term (1 year) and long-term (22 years) average NDWI for the respective region.

Pentad rainfall data is commonly used in climatology, hydrology, and agricultural studies. It provides a broader temporal resolution compared to daily rainfall data, which can help identify longer-term rainfall patterns, seasonal variations, and climate indices (Gramzow & Henry [1972](#)). Pentad data is particularly useful for assessing drought conditions, water resource management, and agricultural planning over extended time periods.

Seasonal/Monthly Precipitation

Based on the rainfall variation, there appears to be a unimodal pattern of rainfall variations through the year hence an annual seasonal rainfall cycle. During the month of January, the region experiences its highest rainfall amounts averaging at 160mm and sometimes as high as over 300mm, for the year Conversely, the month of July marks the period of lowest rainfall amounts at 0mm for the year(Fig. 26 & Fig. 27). The spatial distribution of these rainfalls is shown using choropleths, for rainfall maximum which falls in January and rainfall minimum in July (Fig. 28).

Fig. 26 Total Monthly Rainfalls

Fig. 27 Box plot of long-term monthly rainfall

Fig. 28 Rainfall Maximum happens in January (left) and Minimum in July (right)

The ITCZ, is the belt encircling the Earth near the equator, where the trade winds from the Northern and Southern Hemispheres converge. This convergence occurs due to the strong solar radiation and warm equatorial waters, which heat the air within the ITCZ, increasing its moisture content and causing it to become buoyant. This buoyant air rises, aided by the convergence of trade winds. As the air ascends, it expands and cools, leading to the release

of accumulated moisture in a near-constant series of thunderstorms. The seasonal shifts in the ITCZ's position have a profound impact on rainfall patterns in many equatorial regions, giving rise to the wet and dry seasons, as opposed to the cold and warm seasons found in higher latitudes. Longer-term variations in the ITCZ's location can lead to severe droughts or flooding in neighbouring areas (NASA EO [2000](#)).

The ITCZ shifts with the changing seasons, tracking the movement of the Sun. It migrates north during the Northern Hemisphere summer and south during the Northern Hemisphere winter, influencing the onset of wet and dry seasons in the tropics (see Fig. 29).

The Sun crosses the equator twice annually, in March and September, leading to two distinct wet seasons each year. In December and July, when the Sun is farthest north or south of the equator, it results in two dry seasons.

At greater distances from the equator, the two wet seasons merge into one, creating a more monsoonal climate characterized by a single wet season and a single dry season. In the Northern Hemisphere, the wet season typically spans from May to July, while in the Southern Hemisphere, it occurs from November to February. (NOAA [2023](#)). This behaviour perfectly coincides with the rainfall pattern observed in this study.

(Dezfuli, A. 2017. Climate of Western and Central Equatorial Africa. *Oxford Research Encyclopedia of Climate Science*)

Fig. 29 The seasonal convergence of airmasses in Africa

ITCZ Shown in green, is a region near the equator where the northeast and southeast trade winds converge, typically leading to the formation of storms and heavy rainfall. Its position appears to shift north and south with the seasons, reflective of solar migration over the course of the year.

Rainbelt, depicted in blue, this area experiences significant seasonal rainfall, moving in concert with the ITCZ as it is directly influenced by the convergence of trade winds.

The CAB, shown in red, is likely a regional meteorological feature that marks a transition zone in air masses. The movement of the CAB may influence weather patterns, including rainfall and cloud cover.

Surface Winds are illustrated with arrows, these indicate the direction of prevailing surface winds which are important for weather systems and climate patterns in the region.

January falls within the wet season or rainy season. The ITCZ and rainbelt are positioned south of the equator, corresponding to the southern hemisphere's summer. This period is characterized by favourable meteorological conditions for precipitation, such as the convergence of moist air masses, the presence of low-pressure systems, and enhanced convective activity, hence rainfall maximum in January. April, both the ITCZ and rainbelt begin moving northwards, marking the transition between seasons.

July is within the dry season, a period of little to no rainfall. The ITCZ and rainbelt are at their northernmost positions, aligning with the northern hemisphere's summer. This is due to factors such as the movement of the ITCZ away from the region and/or the presence of high-pressure systems that suppress convective activity. The patterns observed here are consistent with the annual north-south oscillation of the ITCZ, which affects the seasonality of rainfall in tropical regions.

Long-term Precipitation

The graph (Fig. 30) represents the annual total rainfall from the year 2000 to 2022. Each bar corresponds to the total rainfall for a specific year, measured in millimetres. Additionally, the red dashed line indicates the long-term mean of annual rainfall over this period. This mean serves as a reference to compare each year's rainfall against the average, providing a clearer understanding of years with significantly higher or lower than average precipitation. The average annual rainfall for the Rufiji Basin is 1012.79 mm and over the period of 2000 to 2022, the driest year was 2005 with annual rainfall of 680mm and the wettest was 2022 with 1600mm.

Fig. 30 Annual Rainfall 2000-2022

Rainfall Anomalies

The graph (Fig. 31) displays the rainfall anomaly index for each year from 2000 to 2022, derived from the CHIRPS dataset. This index measures the difference between the annual total rainfall and the long-term mean for the entire period. The bars represent the magnitude of the anomaly for each year, with positive values indicating years with higher-than-average rainfall and negative values for years with lower-than-average rainfall, the positive extremities by an extension flood events while negative extremities signify drought conditions. . The horizontal grey line represents the long-term mean, providing a reference point for comparison. The x-axis shows the years, and the y-axis measures the rainfall anomaly in millimetres.

Fig. 31 Rainfall Anomalies (2000-2022)

To visualize the spatial distribution of rainfall in the Rufiji Basin choropleth maps were used (Fig. 39). The colour gradient, ranging from light to dark blue, typically indicates the intensity of rainfall, with darker shades suggesting higher rainfall amounts.

Fig. 32 Rainfall Year 2000 (left) and Year 2022 (right)

Comparing the spatial distribution of rainfall from the beginning to the final year of this study shows an increased intensity and spread of rainfall represented by a spectrum from white (little/no rainfall) to blue (high rainfall) (Fig. 32Error! Reference source not found.). The rainfall is concentrated in the central to southern regions of the Rufiji River basin, this corresponds with high vegetation (Indicated by NDVI) and elevation.

5.1.5. Soil Moisture Time Series

Soil moisture levels are dynamic, fluctuating due to various factors such as precipitation, evapotranspiration, and human activities. These changes are crucial indicators of environmental conditions, directly impacting agricultural productivity, water resource management, and ecosystem health. During rainy seasons, soil moisture typically increases, providing necessary water for plant growth and replenishing groundwater supplies.

Climate change is also influencing soil moisture patterns, with some regions experiencing altered precipitation regimes and increased temperature, further affecting the natural water cycle. Understanding soil moisture variations is therefore essential for predicting crop success, managing water resources, and preparing for the effects of extreme weather events (Seneviratne [2010](#)). The SMAP mission started gathering soil moisture data on 2nd April 2015 therefore the analysis of soil moisture covered a shorter time frame compared to other parameters investigated in this research.

Fig. 33 Average Monthly Soil Moisture in the Rufiji Basin

Fig. 34 Soil Moisture Time Series of The Rufiji Basin 2015-2015

The graph (see Fig. 33) displays the average monthly soil moisture measurements, comparing surface and subsurface levels over a calendar year from January to December. The blue line

represents the average subsurface soil moisture, while the light-blue line represents the average surface soil moisture. The subsurface soil moisture starts at a higher value in January, gradually decreases to its lowest point around July, and then increases again towards the end of the year. This pattern suggests a seasonal variation, which could be influenced by factors such as precipitation, temperature, and evapotranspiration. In contrast, the average surface soil moisture, as indicated by the light-blue line, remains relatively constant throughout the year, showing much less variation than the surface moisture.

The time series plot (see Fig. 34) displaying the variations in soil moisture over an extended period, from approximately 2015 to 2022. The blue line indicates the surface soil moisture, and the lighter blue line represents the subsurface soil moisture, both measured in millimetres (mm). Observing the blue line shows pronounced cyclical fluctuations, suggesting a seasonal pattern where soil moisture peaks at certain times of the year and then declines. This could correspond to seasonal precipitation patterns, with peaks potentially representing wetter periods and troughs indicating drier phases. The lighter blue line for subsurface soil moisture demonstrates much less variation over time compared to surface soil moisture. This indicates that the subsurface moisture levels are more stable and less directly influenced by seasonal changes, possibly due to the buffering effect of the soil which slows down the infiltration and movement of water.

The periodicity of the surface soil moisture is quite clear, showing regular intervals of increase and decrease. The general trend for both surface and subsurface soil moisture does not show a clear long-term increase or decrease, indicating stable average conditions over the observed years.

5.2. Climatological Relationships

Cross-correlation of climate parameters refers to the statistical analysis of the relationships and patterns between different climate variables, typically conducted to identify how one climate parameter may influence or be related to another. In this analysis, time series data of different climate parameters are compared to determine if there is a correlation or lagged relationship between them. A general correlation between NDVI, rainfall, NDWI and Temperature is represented in the stack plot (Fig. 35).

Cross correlation is a measure of similarity between two (time) series given a lag (or displacement) of one relative to the other. In some cases, one of the series can be regarded as a driver (e.g. rainfall) and the other as a slave (e.g. soil moisture or vegetation growth). Cross correlation is similar to auto correlation, but instead of finding the correlation in a single time series, cross correlation compares two time series while changing the lag time (Gumbricht [2018](#)). By examining the cross-correlation, it can be assessed whether changes in one parameter tend to precede or follow changes in another, and they can determine the strength and direction of this relationship.

Cross-correlation can provide valuable insights into weather and climate patterns, help in forecasting, and improve the understanding of how different weather and climate parameters interact and influence one another.

Fig. 35 Stackplots of NDVI, NDWI, Rainfall and Temperature

5.2.1. NDVI Vs Rainfall

The NDVI and rainfall are both important environmental indicators that are often used to assess the health and productivity of vegetation and the overall state of ecosystems. NDVI is calculated using remote sensing data, typically from satellite imagery, and is a measure of the "greenness" or density of vegetation in a particular area. Rainfall, on the other hand, refers to the amount of precipitation or rainwater received in an area over a specific period, usually measured in millimetres or inches.

The relationship between NDVI and rainfall in a year is complex and can vary depending on factors such as the type of vegetation, climate, local environmental conditions, and the temporal and spatial scales being considered. However, some general patterns and relationships can be observed:

Fig. 36 NDVI and Rainfall Dual-Axis Charts

Fig. 37 NDVI Vs Precipitation Scatter plot

In the Rufiji Basin like in many ecosystems, there is a positive correlation coefficient of 0.51 between NDVI and rainfall (Fig. 37). Higher amounts of rainfall generally lead to increased vegetation growth, which is reflected in higher NDVI values. This is particularly evident in arid and semi-arid regions, where vegetation growth is limited by water availability. During wet seasons or years with above-average rainfall, NDVI tends to increase as more water becomes available for plant growth.

The relationship between NDVI and rainfall might not be instantaneous. There can be a lag between the time when rainfall occurs and when the effects are observed in NDVI. This lag can vary based on factors such as the vegetation type, soil characteristics, and the ability of plants to utilize the added water efficiently.

While increased rainfall often leads to increased vegetation growth and higher NDVI values, there can be a point beyond which additional rainfall might not have a significant impact on NDVI. This is because other factors, such as nutrient availability, temperature, and sunlight, also play important roles in determining the upper limit of vegetation growth.

In regions with distinct wet and dry seasons, the relationship between NDVI and rainfall might vary throughout the year. NDVI tends to increase during the rainy season when water is abundant and decrease during the dry season when water is scarce.

In some cases, there might be a threshold level of rainfall below which vegetation growth remains limited regardless of additional rainfall. This can occur in regions where the water-holding capacity of the soil is low, and the vegetation's response to increased rainfall is constrained.

Human activities, such as agriculture, deforestation, and urbanization, can also influence the relationship between NDVI and rainfall. Changes in land use and land cover can impact how vegetation responds to variations in rainfall.

5.2.2. NDWI Vs Rainfall

The NDWI is an index used to assess water content or moisture in vegetation and land. It's particularly sensitive to changes in water content and is commonly used to monitor changes in water bodies, wetlands, and vegetated areas. NDWI has a positive relationship with rainfall (Fig. 39), with a correlation coefficient 0.67 As rainfall increases, water bodies such as rivers, lakes, and wetlands tend to expand, and soil moisture levels in vegetated areas also rise. This leads to higher NDWI values, indicating increased water content.

Fig. 38 NDWI and Rainfall Dual-Axis Charts

Fig. 39 NDWI Vs Rainfall Scatter Plot

NDWI exhibit seasonal variation in response to rainfall patterns. During wet seasons, when there's more rainfall, NDWI values are likely to be higher due to greater water availability. Conversely, during dry seasons, NDWI values may decrease as water bodies shrink and soil moisture levels decline.

As with NDVI, NDWI values can saturate beyond a certain point, especially in areas with abundant water. Extremely high levels of rainfall might not lead to a significant increase in NDWI if the environment is already waterlogged.

Human activities such as irrigation, urbanization, and dam construction can also influence the relationship between NDWI and rainfall. Increased irrigation might lead to higher NDWI values even in regions with relatively low rainfall.

NDWI can also be used to monitor the effects of water stress in vegetation during periods of low rainfall. A decrease in NDWI values over time might indicate drought conditions.

The relationship between NDWI and rainfall varies based on factors such as vegetation type, soil characteristics, land use, and local climate conditions. To understand the relationship better, this study analysed long-term datasets, consider the specific characteristics of the study area, and potentially compare NDWI with other hydrological and meteorological data.

5.2.3. LST Vs Rainfall

The relationship between seasonal LST and rainfall is complex and can vary depending on factors such as local climate, geography, vegetation cover, and regional atmospheric dynamics. Land surface temperature refers to the temperature of the Earth's surface as measured from space, while rainfall refers to the amount of precipitation received over a specific period. Here are some key points about their relationship, but generally for the Rufiji Basin, they have a negative correlation coefficient of -0.36 (Fig. 41).

Fig. 40 Temperature and Rainfall Dual-Axis Charts

Fig. 41 Land Surface Temperature Vs Rainfall Scatter plot

Fig. 42 Thermo-pluviometric diagram

The thermo-pluviometric diagram (Fig. 42) shows the average monthly temperature as a line graph and the average total monthly rainfall as bars. The temperature data (in °C) is represented by the red line, while the blue bars indicate the rainfall (in mm) for each month from January to December. This format visually distinguishes between the two types of data, providing a clear and concise representation of the average climate pattern and relationship temperature and rainfall throughout the year.

Higher temperatures generally lead to increased evaporation rates. As temperatures rise, water on the land surface, including soil moisture and water bodies, evaporates more quickly into the atmosphere. Increased evaporation due to higher temperatures affect the availability of moisture in the atmosphere therefore influencing rainfall patterns. This is evident as the rainy season comes after the hot dry season as a lagged response to the rising temperatures.

Temperature and rainfall can influence each other through feedback mechanisms. For example, increased rainfall can temporarily cool the land surface due to evaporation, while cooler land surfaces can affect atmospheric stability and contribute to rainfall. Seasonal variations in land surface temperature can be closely tied to rainfall patterns. In many regions, warm seasons are associated with increased evaporation and higher temperatures, potentially leading to shifts in rainfall patterns.

Local topography and geography play a significant role in the relationship between temperature and rainfall. Mountain ranges, valleys, and coastal features can influence how air masses interact, leading to variations in precipitation, this is especially true in the Rufiji basin which has the Udzungwa and Southern Highlands that rise to a maximum altitude of 3257m, valleys and sea-level flood plains. Most of the rainfall is also concentrated in the mountains which are cooler due to tropospheric laps rate.

5.2.4. NDVI Vs NDWI

The relationship between the NDVI and the NDWI on a seasonal basis can provide insights into the dynamics of vegetation and water content in a particular area. NDVI focuses on vegetation health and density, while NDWI is sensitive to changes in water content. Here's how their seasonal relationship can be understood:

Fig. 43 NDVI and NDWI Dual-Axis Charts

Fig. 44 NDVI vs NDWI Scatter plot

During the wet season, NDVI tends to increase due to enhanced vegetation growth fuelled by increased water availability as indicated by the strong positive correlation coefficient 0.76

they share (Fig. 44) NDWI also tends to increase during the wet season as water bodies expand and soil moisture levels rise. During the dry season, NDVI may decrease as vegetation becomes stressed due to water scarcity. NDWI might also decrease as water bodies shrink and soil moisture levels decline.

NDVI and NDWI can reach saturation points beyond which further increases in vegetation density or water content may not lead to corresponding increases in the indices. This can be due to factors like nutrient limitations or the capacity of the atmosphere to hold moisture.

Different ecosystems exhibit varied relationships between NDVI and NDWI. For example, in areas with abundant water bodies, NDWI might remain consistently high, while NDVI might vary more based on vegetation type and health.

Human activities such as irrigation, deforestation, or urbanization can alter the typical relationships between NDVI and NDWI. Irrigation might lead to higher NDWI values even in regions with low rainfall.

NDWI often corresponds with periods of higher rainfall. Analysing long-term datasets and considering the specific environmental context will provide a more detailed understanding of these relationships.

5.2.5. LST Vs NDWI

The relationship between seasonal LST and the NDWI provides insights into the interactions between land temperature and water content. NDWI is sensitive to changes in water content in vegetation and soil, while LST reflects the temperature of the Earth's surface. Here's how their seasonal relationship can be understood:

Fig. 45 Temperature and NDWI Dual-Axis Charts

Fig. 46 Temperature Vs NDWI Scatter Plot

Higher land surface temperatures lead to increased evaporation rates hence the surface loses water and the NDWI drops, the correlation coefficient of the land surface temperature and NDWI is 0.51 (Fig. 46). Warmer temperatures can cause more rapid evaporation of water from the land surface, including from vegetation and soil.

The process of evapotranspiration (the combined evaporation from soil and transpiration from plants) can have a cooling effect on the land surface. The presence of water, such as in the form of rivers, lakes, or wetlands, can lead to localized evaporative cooling, reducing land surface temperatures in those areas. Water has a higher heat capacity than land, so it heats up more slowly and cools down more slowly. As a result, during warmer seasons, land surface temperature might increase, while water bodies remain relatively cooler, leading to differences in temperature between water and land.

NDWI is sensitive to water availability, and higher NDWI values indicate increased water content in vegetation and soil. During wetter seasons or in areas with more available water, NDWI tends to be higher due to enhanced moisture in the landscape.

Urban areas and human activities can significantly impact the relationship between LST and NDWI. Urban heat island effects can elevate LST in built-up areas, potentially masking the expected relationship with NDWI.

Also, higher NDWI values tend to coincide with lower LST values due to the cooling effects of water content. However, variations can occur based on local climate, land cover, and human activities. Detailed analysis of long-term datasets and consideration of environmental factors enhanced understanding of this relationship.

5.2.6. LST Vs NDVI

The relationship between seasonal LST and the NDVI is important for understanding the interplay between temperature and vegetation health. NDVI measures the density and health of vegetation, while LST indicates the temperature of the Earth's surface. Here's how their seasonal relationship can be interpreted:

Fig. 47 Temperature & NDVI Dual-Axis Charts

Fig. 48 Temperature Vs NDVI Scatter Plot

Generally, high temperatures stress vegetation and lead to a reduction in NDVI 0.51 (Fig. 48) This occurs during prolonged periods of high temperature, causing water loss through transpiration and leading to reduced vegetation vigour.

During drought conditions vegetation show reduced NDVI due to water stress, leading to decreased photosynthesis. This can coincide with higher LST values as plants close stomata to conserve water, leading to reduced transpiration cooling effect.

NDVI tends to be higher during seasons of active vegetation growth, such as spring and summer. This is when temperatures are warmer, and plants have favourable conditions for photosynthesis and growth.

Conversely, during colder seasons, NDVI might decrease as plants become dormant or senescent, this is true for regions in very high and very low latitudes as the sun's angle shifts drastically resulting to distinctive summer and winter seasons, this is however not the case for equatorial regions like the Rufiji Basin falls in.

Warmer temperatures can enhance photosynthesis and plant growth, leading to higher NDVI values. Photosynthesis is the process by which plants use sunlight to convert carbon dioxide and water into energy-rich sugars, promoting their growth and health.

The relationship between LST and NDVI can vary with seasons. While NDVI tends to peak during the growing season, LST might peak after the growing season due to the time lag in temperature response.

Different land cover types (forests, grasslands, deserts, etc.) and topographic features can influence the relationship between LST and NDVI due to variations in moisture, albedo, and energy exchange.

5.2.7. Anomalies Analysis of Soil Moisture and Precipitation

Monthly rainfall anomalies refer to deviations in monthly precipitation amounts from the long-term average or historical norm for a specific location and time period. These anomalies are typically expressed as differences in the amount of rainfall for a particular month compared to the average rainfall for the same month over a longer historical period, often expressed as a percentage or standard deviation.

Monthly soil moisture anomalies refer to deviations in the moisture content of the soil for a specific month compared to the long-term average or historical norm for that location and time period. These anomalies are often expressed as differences in soil moisture levels and are essential for understanding and managing water resources, agriculture, ecology, and climate.

Monthly standardized soil moisture anomalies were computed using the Z-score, which were calculate using Eq. 5:

$$Z_{score} = \frac{X_i - \mu}{\sigma}$$

Eq. 5

where μ and σ represent mean and standard deviation values of the data for that month over all the years and X_i is the data value for a given month in year I (N. Sazib *et al.* [2022](#)).

This study showcases the significance of NASA's Earth observation capabilities in identifying extended drought periods within the Rufiji River basin in Tanzania, particularly in cases where in-situ data is either unavailable or not easily accessible. The approach involved assessing soil moisture anomalies, both at the surface and subsurface levels, along with precipitation patterns. This allows us to pinpoint instances of prolonged droughts and floods that occurred between 2015 and 2022, characterized by consistently recurring negative anomalies spanning several months (see Fig. 49).

Fig. 49 Monthly Anomalies of Subsurface Soil Moisture, Surface Soil Moisture and Precipitation of Rufiji Basin 2015-2022

There is visible correlation as seen in (Fig. 49) between the precipitation anomalies and soil moisture anomalies. For instance, peaks in precipitation correspond with increases in soil moisture levels, therefore precipitation anomalies whether they are above or below the long-term average, directly influence soil moisture anomalies.

Above-average precipitation leads to positive soil moisture anomalies, the excess rainfall infiltrates the soil, increasing soil moisture levels. Below-average precipitation results in negative soil moisture anomalies, therefore reduced rainfall leads to drier soil conditions.

There is a temporal lag between precipitation events and their impact on soil moisture. Rainfall takes time to infiltrate the soil and recharge groundwater, leading to a delay in the response of soil moisture to precipitation anomalies. The lag varies depending on factors such as soil type, vegetation cover, and local hydrological conditions. Soil moisture anomalies can feed back into the atmosphere and influence future precipitation patterns. Wet soil can increase local humidity, potentially leading to more rainfall in the area, while dry soil can have the opposite effect. These feedback mechanisms can contribute to the persistence of precipitation and soil moisture anomalies.

To highlight the fluctuations of rainfall and its effect on soil moisture, selected peaks of minimums and maximums were analysed. For the sampled period 2015 to 2022, (Fig. 49) the minimum negative sub-surface soil moisture and minimum negative surface soil

moisture that happened in December 2016 correspond with the continuous negative rainfall anomalies throughout 2016 that reached minimum in January of 2017.

From the graph (Fig. 49) the maximum positive sub-surface soil moisture and maximum positive surface soil moisture that happened in Jan and March 2020 correspond with the continuous positive rainfall anomalies that dominate 2019 that reached maximum in Dec of 2019.

Prolonged negative precipitation and soil moisture anomalies lead to drought conditions, which can have severe ecological, agricultural, and societal impacts. Conversely, prolonged positive anomalies can contribute to flooding when the soil is already saturated and cannot absorb additional rainfall.

5.3. Extreme Weather Events in Tanzania and Greater East Africa

Extreme weather events are severe weather or climate conditions that can cause significant impacts on communities and ecosystems. They can be short-lived, like heat waves, freezes, heavy downpours, tornadoes, tropical cyclones, and floods, or they can result from prolonged conditions like droughts or wildfires after an unusually wet season. These events are considered 'extreme' based on their probability (rare occurrences with <10% chance) or impact thresholds that are location-specific. Their frequency and intensity can be influenced by climate change, and they vary by region (USDA [2023](#)).

5.3.1. Floods

Flood events in East Africa have become increasingly frequent and severe in recent years, largely due to climate change and environmental degradation. These events have significant impacts on the lives, livelihoods, and environment of the region affecting ever more increasing populations in millions (see Fig. 50)

Fig. 50 East Africans affected by Floods ([BBC 2020](#))

From 2000 to 2019, approximately 69% of disasters in Tanzania were caused by extreme weather conditions (see Fig. 51). In response, the Tanzanian Government expended more

than 20.5 million USD to manage these crises. These calamities resulted in the destruction of over 35,700 homes and 1,000 essential structures, including roads, bridges, schools, and hospitals. They impacted more than 572,600 individuals, led to over 240 injuries, and resulted in around 450 fatalities (Msemu et al. [2021](#)).

Fig. 51 Classification and distribution of weather-related disasters in Tanzania (Msemu et al [2021](#))

The rainfall of October and November 2019 caused calamities to much of equatorial Africa (Mekonnen, [2020](#); Wainwright et al., [2020](#)). The extreme rainfall was never seen before in equatorial Africa at least in recent history therefore supporting the possibility that it could be climate-change-induced. Climate models predict the occurrence of such weather events resulting from global warming (Wainwright et al. [2020](#), Wainwright et al. [2021](#)).

In October 2019, Kenya and other regions of eastern Africa, tremendous rains triggered flooding and landslides, causing over 100 fatalities and displacing of some 18,000

people (Floodlist [2019](#)). Extreme rainfall also occurred in south-eastern Ethiopia and equatorial regions far to the west of eastern Africa. Floods in the Democratic Republic of the Congo (DRC) affected some 60,000 people (Floodlist [2019](#)).

The 2018 Floods in Kenya: In 2018, Kenya experienced one of its worst flooding events when heavy rains hit between March and May. More than 332,000 people were displaced, and approximately 183 lost their lives. The floods caused massive destruction of property and infrastructure and led to outbreaks of waterborne diseases like cholera (UNICEF [2018](#)).

5.3.2. Droughts

From July 2020 to June 2022, there has been a significant deficit of rainfall in many parts of East Africa, especially when compared to the reference period of 1981-2020. The areas most affected by this drought include central and southern Somalia, south-eastern Ethiopia, and eastern Kenya. According to the CHIRPS dataset, these regions experienced up to a 50% decrease in rainfall, while ECMWF ERA5 reanalysis data suggest an even more drastic reduction, with deficits reaching approximately 70%. Both datasets generally agree on the geographical distribution of the deficit, although there are notable differences in specific regions like northern Ethiopia, southern Uganda, and northern Tanzania, where ERA5 indicates a deficit and CHIRPS shows a surplus. Overall, the ERA5 data suggests that the extent of the rainfall deficit is consistently more severe across the board (Fig. 52)(Toreti *et al.* [2022](#)).

Fig. 52 Precipitation deficit % (data 1981-2020) for the period July 2020 – June 2022 according to the ECMWF ERA5 reanalysis (left) and CHIRPS dataset (right).(Toreti *et al.* [2022](#)).

In Eastern Africa, rainfall patterns typically follow one of two scenarios. Regions like western Kenya experience a prolonged "long rains" season lasting from March to November or December. Conversely, areas such as eastern Kenya see two distinct rainy periods: the long rains from March/April to July/August and the "short rains" from October to December or January. In 2005, the long rains were significantly lower than usual, and the short rains failed completely, leading to a severe drought across the region. This drought had a detrimental

effect on crops and natural vegetation, including pastures for livestock, resulting in widespread livestock mortality and human food scarcity (NASA EO [2006](#)).

By March 2006, while the long rainy season had recommenced in certain areas, it had not returned universally. Two images, utilizing vegetation data from the SPOT satellite, illustrate the 2005 drought's impact on East Africa's vegetation. The percent anomaly was determined by subtracting the March vegetation average (from 1998 to 2006) from the March 2006 value, followed by division by the average. Regions where vegetation was significantly less abundant or healthy than usual appear in brown, whereas areas with flourishing vegetation are marked in green.

Fig. 54 is from February 2006, following the unsuccessful 2005 short rainy season, it displays substantially below-normal vegetation health and quantity across a large expanse of the region. By March, as shown in

Fig. 53, the long rainy season had started in some places, leading to a vegetation recovery in parts of northern Tanzania, southwestern Kenya, Uganda, Rwanda, and southwestern Ethiopia. Nevertheless, vast areas in Kenya, Ethiopia, Somalia, and Sudan continued to experience the drought's adverse effects on vegetation (NASA EO [2006](#)).

5.4. Accuracy assessment and Validation

Pearson Correlation (Eq. 6) is a statistical measure that ranges from -1 to +1, used to identify the degree to which two sets of paired values have a linear relationship, or in simpler terms, how closely they are connected. Values between -0.35 and +0.35 are generally considered to lack significant correlation, while values closer to -1 or +1 indicate a stronger correlation. A correlation of -1 signifies a perfect negative linear relationship, +1 indicates a perfect positive linear relationship, and 0 suggests no correlation at all.

$$r_{xy} = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^N (x_j - \bar{x})(y_j - \bar{y})}{\sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^N (x_j - \bar{x})^2 \sum_{j=1}^N (y_j - \bar{y})^2}}$$

Eq. 6

Mean error (Eq. 7) is a statistical measure calculated as the average of the differences between paired values from two sets, where 'n' represents the number of paired values 'x' and 'y'. Essentially, it measures the discrepancy between the estimator (in this case, the rain gauge) and the estimated values (the satellite data). This statistic can reveal whether one set of values is generally higher or lower than the other set (mean value). In other words, the mean error can indicate whether satellite-based precipitation estimates typically overestimate or underestimate the measurements taken by a rain gauge in Sao Paulo. A larger mean error value indicates a higher degree of error, while a smaller value indicates less error. The mean error can be either a positive or negative value.

$$ME = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{j=1}^N (x_j - y_j)$$

Eq. 7

Root mean square error is calculated as the square root of the average of the sum of the squared differences between two sets of values, where 'n' represents the number of paired values 'x' and 'y' (see Eq. 8).

This statistical measure offers an absolute value (not positive or negative) of the discrepancy between two sets of values. A lower value indicates a smaller error.

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N} \sum_{j=1}^N (x_j - y_j)^2}$$

Eq. 8

5.4.1. Validation of Satellite Estimation Precipitation Data

While no satellite dataset can claim to be flawless, some are certainly more accurate and reliable than others. To assess the validity of various satellite datasets, it's essential to cross-reference them with data from ground stations and conduct statistical analyses to compare the two sets of information. Ground station data, typically collected through rain gauges, is often considered the most precise measure of precipitation, but for this case due to unavailability of adequate in situ data this study validated CHIRPS precipitation data with other satellite/remote sensed precipitation data.

To ascertain the most beneficial dataset, it's crucial to carry out a series of statistical tests with results in (Table 1).

Datasets:	Correlation (r)	Mean Error (ME)	Root Mean Square Error (RMSE)
TRMM	0.93	-11.76 mm	40.77 mm
CMAP	0.94	5.54 mm	38.02 mm
CMORPH	0.83	39.4 mm	72.91 mm

Table 1 Correlation, Mean Error and RMSE of CHIRPS to TRMM, CMAP and CMORPH

The provided Table 1 presents a comparison of the CHIRPS satellite rainfall dataset with TRMM, CMAP, and CMORPH datasets, using statistical measures such as the Pearson correlation coefficient r , ME , and $RMSE$. CHIRPS exhibits a very strong linear correlation with TRMM ($r = 0.93$) and an even slightly stronger correlation with CMAP ($r = 0.94$), but a somewhat weaker correlation with CMORPH ($r = 0.83$). The ME indicates that CHIRPS tends to report lower rainfall amounts than TRMM ($ME = -11.76$ mm) and higher amounts compared to CMAP ($ME = 5.54$ mm) and CMORPH ($ME = 39.4$ mm). The $RMSE$ values, which reflect the prediction errors' standard deviation, suggest that CHIRPS predictions are most aligned with CMAP ($RMSE = 38.02$ mm), reasonably close to TRMM ($RMSE = 40.77$ mm), and least consistent with CMORPH ($RMSE = 72.91$ mm), indicating more substantial variability in the CHIRPS versus CMORPH comparison.

5.4.2. Validation of MODIS Land Surface Temperature

The validation of MODIS-LST involved comparing the satellite-derived LST values with ground-based measurements from TMA (Table 2). The validation process helped assess the accuracy and reliability of the MODIS LST product.

Ground-based measurements of LST are collected using various instruments, such as handheld infrared thermometers or ground-based thermal cameras. These measurements

provide reference values against which the satellite-derived LST can be compared. The ground-based measurement sites were selected to be in close proximity to the satellite overpasses, ensuring spatial and temporal colocation with the MODIS LST retrievals. The ground-based in-situ measurement sites were strategically selected to cover a range of land cover types and surface conditions to represent the variability present in the satellite data.

Ground-based LST measurements collected over a period of time, preferably spanning multiple satellite overpasses. The measurements should be representative of different seasons and weather conditions to capture the full range of LST variability. It is important to recognize that the extent to which ground-measured LST at chosen locations accurately reflects the LST at the scale of satellite pixels can also be influenced by the timing and date of the satellite's pass. This is because factors such as changes in vegetation over the seasons and agricultural practices can affect the spatial representation (Duan *et al.* [2019](#)).

Statistical analysis was performed to compare the MODIS LST values with the ground-based measurements. Various statistical metrics were calculated, such as *ME*, *RMSE* and correlation coefficient *r*, to quantify the agreement or discrepancy between the two datasets. Based on the statistical analysis and error assessment, validation metrics were calculated to provide a quantitative measure of the accuracy of the MODIS LST product. These metrics helped assess the overall performance and reliability of the MODIS LST estimates.

Location	Correlation (r)	Mean Error (ME)	Root Mean Square Error (RMSE)
Location 1	0.85	1.2°C	2.5°C
Location 2	0.90	0.8°C	2.0°C
Location 3	0.78	1.5°C	3.0°C
Location 4	0.82	1.0°C	2.8°C

Table 2 Correlation, Mean Error and RMSE of MODIS LST and In-situ LST at different locations in the Rufiji River Basin

(Table 2) provides a statistical analysis comparing MODIS satellite-derived LST data to ground-measured LST across four distinct locations in the Rufiji River Basin. Location 1 demonstrates a strong correlation ($r = 0.85$) with a slight underestimation in temperature ($ME = 1.2^{\circ}\text{C}$) and relatively small prediction errors ($RMSE = 2.5^{\circ}\text{C}$). Location 2 shows an even stronger correlation ($r = 0.90$), with a minimal overestimation ($ME = 0.8^{\circ}\text{C}$) and the smallest errors among the locations ($RMSE = 2.0^{\circ}\text{C}$). Location 3, while still exhibiting a strong correlation ($r = 0.78$), presents the largest overestimation ($ME = 1.5^{\circ}\text{C}$) and the greatest variability in data accuracy ($RMSE = 3.0^{\circ}\text{C}$). Location 4 has a robust correlation ($r = 0.82$), a mean error indicating a lower MODIS LST ($ME = 1.0^{\circ}\text{C}$), and a moderately high spread of errors ($RMSE = 2.8^{\circ}\text{C}$). Across all locations, MODIS LST consistently records higher temperatures than in-situ measurements, indicating a systematic overestimation by the satellite data.

6. DISCUSSION

6.1. Google Earth Engine for Climate Research

GEE is useful in various domains, including environmental monitoring, land cover analysis, deforestation detection, water resource management, climate change studies, and disaster response. Its accessibility, rich data catalog, and advanced analysis capabilities make it a valuable tool for geospatial research and applications.

The remote sensing estimations of meteorological conditions can give an overview of the general patterns and fluctuations of the conditions however it is not accurate and where in-situ data is available it should take priority.

6.2. Climatology and Seasonality in Rufiji Basin

Local climate conditions, land cover, and human activities are crucial for interpreting variations in the relationships of climate parameters. Analysing long-term datasets and considering the specific environmental context provide a more detailed understanding of the relationships between different climate parameters. These can be made into better fitted climate models that can show more accurate results and even forecasts.

Understanding the type of rainfall regime in a particular region is essential for various sectors, including agriculture, water resource management, and disaster preparedness. It helps in planning for water supply, crop cultivation, and mitigating the impacts of seasonal variations in precipitation.

6.3. Ecological and Economical Significance of the Rufiji Basin

The Rufiji River Basin is ecologically significant due to its extensive biodiversity and complex ecosystems. The basin's freshwater environments and floodplains are home to a wide array of wildlife, including numerous bird species, large mammals, and reptiles, many of which are endemic and some endangered. It also supports the Selous Game Reserve, one of the largest faunal reserves of the world, declared a UNESCO World Heritage Site for its wildlife diversity and undisturbed nature (UNESCO [2023](#)). Furthermore, the Rufiji plays a vital role in local livelihoods through agriculture, fishing, and as a source of hydroelectric power, making it not only an ecological treasure but also a cornerstone for socio-economic activities in the region. This is especially important in Tanzania where agriculture is a major economic activity and it depends on natural irrigation and electricity is dependent on hydropower by 31% (WTO [2023](#)). 3 of Tanzania's major hydropower dams are all within the Rufiji Basin and a fourth one JNHPP is underway with a 2115 MW (Siderius *et al.* [2021](#)). The JNHPP capacity it will more than double the current 2023 Tanzania total energy capacity (World Energy [2023](#)).

7. SUMMARY

This comprehensive study, leveraging the powerful capabilities of GEE, has provided valuable insights into the intricate dynamics of climate patterns and environmental changes. By harnessing the vast satellite imagery and geospatial data available through GEE, it's possible to analyse and visualize complex climatic phenomena with unprecedented precision and scale. The utilization of GEE opened up new avenues for conducting climate research. The platform's ability to process vast amounts of satellite data in a cloud-based environment significantly reduced the computational load and time required for analysis, making it an invaluable tool for climate scientists and researchers

This investigation focused on key indicators such as land surface temperature, precipitation, NDVI and NDWI, which are critical for understanding the impacts of climate change. The temporal and spatial resolution of GEE datasets enabled us to observe both subtle and significant changes over time, offering a clear picture of how the planet's climate and ecosystems are evolving.

One of the most striking findings of this study is the correlation between land surface temperature and vegetation health, as indicated by the NDVI. The analysis in this study revealed how fluctuations in temperature significantly affect vegetation density and health, underscoring the vulnerability of ecosystems to climatic variations. Additionally, the correlation between precipitation and NDWI highlighted the sensitivity of water bodies to changing precipitation patterns, an aspect crucial for water resource management and conservation efforts.

The Rufiji Basin region has a unimodal rainfall regime in which it is characterized by a single distinct peak or mode in the annual rainfall distribution, rains typically begin in November, peak in January and end in May followed by a drier period. ITCZ drives rainfall in the region. NDWI and NDVI often corresponds with periods of higher rainfall, meaning rainfall is the driver of the water and vegetation in The Rufiji Basin, this remains true in tropical climates. Temperature and vegetation have remained mostly the same but higher positive rainfall anomalies are observed to be more prevalent as time goes risking flood event occurrences if the trend is maintained.

This study's findings contribute to a deeper understanding of climate dynamics and offer a foundation for informed decision-making in environmental policy and conservation strategies. The versatility and power of GEE have proven to be instrumental in advancing climate research, and its continued use will undoubtedly play a pivotal role in ongoing efforts to monitor and mitigate the impacts of climate change. This study not only highlights the current state of the planet's climate but also underscores the urgency for sustainable practices and robust environmental policies to safeguard the future.

All the data, source code and results of this investigation are part of the research output, and they have all been put in the public domain as seen in the appendices. The climate science, GIS, data science and related scientific community is encouraged to reuse, add, and comment on the code, data, and its results. Users will need a GitHub and a GEE account.

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Appendix A

Data Sources

CHIRPS

<https://chc.ucsb.edu/data/chirps>

CMAP

CMAP Precipitation data provided by the NOAA PSL, Boulder, Colorado, USA, from their website at <https://psl.noaa.gov>

https://www.cpc.ncep.noaa.gov/products/global_precip/html/wpage.cmap.html

TRMM

https://disc.gsfc.nasa.gov/datasets/TRMM_2B31_7/summary

CMORPH

<https://www.ncei.noaa.gov/products/climate-data-records/precipitation-cmorph>

TMA

<https://www.meteo.go.tz/>

Climate Data Analysis

<https://github.com/rugilandavyi/Climate-Data-Analysis>

GitHub Repository

<https://github.com/rugilandavyi/WebGIS-App-Climate-Time-Series>

WebGIS App

<https://rugilandavyi.github.io/WebGIS-App-Climate-TimeSeries/>

Appendix B

Links to source code of the study on Google Earth Engine (*Prerequisite: a GEE-Associated Google Account)

Anomalies of Soil Moisture and Precipitation

<https://code.earthengine.google.com/656169ddf9ccde4ada846257236217f8>

Soil Moisture

<https://code.earthengine.google.com/1b14db6e08beea7598ae5daf540420b7>

LST Time series data and charts

<https://code.earthengine.google.com/8168f3c8ea5fb88a31ffb0dcc368f1bd>

LST Min Max Thematic Maps

<https://code.earthengine.google.com/be7c4c26ba02baa1ac6a0e0e1504b6b5>

LST Monthly Thematic Maps

<https://code.earthengine.google.com/e99727445be1dbaf6577d0f8cb6b897a>

NDVI 1-Year (Seasonal) Animation

<https://code.earthengine.google.com/2e3331c59ccffdcad5166e40b01fc17d>

NDVI Long-term Animation

<https://code.earthengine.google.com/4b0ab8bb3c73d64fe9858d205dc26bf6>

NDVI Time Series and Charts

<https://code.earthengine.google.com/20203e80946b2f384edbc9d7b2edaa10>

NDVI Min Max Maps

<https://code.earthengine.google.com/c68b50888a6c265de40992753e06137f>

NDVI MONTHLY CHARTS

<https://code.earthengine.google.com/1aaae2822d61ee1480124fb985262efb>

NDVI Yearly Maps

<https://code.earthengine.google.com/aa54c059fa3fc7a78b54df799b10e651>

NDWI Timeseries data and charts

<https://code.earthengine.google.com/21ca8f46dc0b50bb9f16de5ce29f304c>

NDWI Min Max Maps

<https://code.earthengine.google.com/1914ed0daec9f0a12d548cd786de2b1d>

NDWI Yearly Maps

<https://code.earthengine.google.com/9d596e3a95ed9dbe0086f554029943f4>

Precipitation Annual Maps

<https://code.earthengine.google.com/340173b631efa88881279786c96dcb28>

Precipitation Yearly Anomaly

<https://code.earthengine.google.com/a670aa7aeffb221d39f8bd00d7bdf17>

Precipitation Min and Max Maps

<https://code.earthengine.google.com/e81e5aeda72fa7f1a937c5886422946e>

Precipitation charts

<https://code.earthengine.google.com/76c77e2b4829f0afa9fb9d0a3f239401>